

STEAM roadmap for Science Education in Horizon Europe

Relevant for:

- Research (DG RTD)
- Education (DG EAC)
- Employment (DG EMPL)
- ICT and digital (DG CNECT)
- Expands the STEM strategic plan

What is STEAM?
 Actions categorisation

Research actions

Priority area 1				Priority area 2				Priority area 3				Priority area 4			
Strengthening the STEAM Curriculum at National and EU level				Enhancing Teacher Training and the Learning Environment				Aligning STEAM education and career design with societal and industrial needs - STEAM literate citizens				Promoting equity with transdisciplinary, effective inclusive STEAM education paradigms			
1A		1B		2A		2B		3A		3B		4A		4B	
Redefine STEAM as a Transdisciplinary Curriculum		Develop transdisciplinary STEAM Learning Materials and Teacher Resources		Prioritize STEAM Training for Educators and school/university leaders		Foster inclusive and supportive Learning Environments harnessing AI and digital tools		Develop STEAM career design and integrated learning pathways		Encourage agile partnerships with organizations to address industry and societal needs		Establish flexible, Inclusive and supportive STEAM education		Promote Intersectional approaches in STEAM, improving accessibility	
HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34	HE 2026-27	FP10 2028-34

Mission education: systemic change of the educational system and assessment: skills-focused, transdisciplinary, inclusive, AI-enabled [coordinating with the **European STEM Executive Panel**, **Union of Skills** and **EU national policies**]

Funding Instruments	Horizon/ FP10 (2028-34)	Previously Funded Projects
	Erasmus+	
	Other funding instruments	
	Policy Instruments	

<p>EU Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum / school / university and assessment</p> <p>Investigation of what the arts, design and creativity bring to STEAM education and derive best practices</p>	<p>Development and testing of a EU transdisciplinary STEM-focused curriculum and assessment in lighthouse institutions</p>	<p>Deployment and investigation of education and training through citizen science applied to STEAM</p>	<p>Research on STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment to investigate and test best practices</p>	<p>Deployment and investigation of new approach to teachers' training (pre-service and in-service) for transdisciplinary education</p> <p>Increase STEAM teaching prestige through fostering schools/university collaborations with local actors</p> <p>Doctoral network on STEAM</p> <p>The new role of education/teachers/lecturers in an AI-enhanced STE(A)M education and work environment: arts for fostering equality and wellbeing</p> <p>STEAM cradle to grave</p>	<p>STEAM (lack of) career selection</p> <p>STEAM career design</p> <p>STEAM career exploration centers</p>	<p>Integrate STEAM education in Horizon Europe Pillar 2 calls, in particular Cluster 2</p> <p>STEM Entrepreneurship education</p> <p>Capacity building in public administrations for multi-stakeholder collaborations and co-financing (open-schooling)</p> <p>Joint diplomas, degrees, microcredentials with industry/civic organizations - fast tracking creditization at EU level</p>	<p>An economic case for inclusive STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education</p> <p>Effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning paradigms to support learning preferences and needs of diverse learners to increase inclusivity and improve skills</p> <p>Learning Environment design and its impact on learning outcomes</p>	<p>Investigate the efficacy of policies to increase hybrid and blended learning to make STEAM educational more accessible</p> <p>Mentorship programs and scholarships for underrepresented groups</p>
<p>Systematic organization of open-access STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment, identification of gaps and development in all EU languages with feedback loops for improvement</p> <p>Funding for EDTECH startups to promote STEAM</p> <p>EU Council of societal challenges to introduce a challenge on education</p>	<p>EU University alliance on STEAM</p>	<p>Development of networks, centres and alliances (incl. equipment) of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for mutual learning on STEAM</p> <p>Training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM</p>	<p>Update the Digital Education Plan to have a broader definition of inclusivity</p>					

<https://www.road-steamer.eu/>

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STEAM (lack of) career selection

Investigate the motivation of students exposed and not exposed to STEAM education and open schooling approaches integrating social and corporate collaborations, in selecting a STE(A)M education (secondary/vocational/tertiary) and a career in STE(A)M: identify barriers, enablers and biases.

Examples

Education and Training Monitor 2024 (Finland)

Online resource

Finland education focus on STEM does not increase STEM uptake.

CAREER project

Online resource Project (Funded) Non formal

funded by an ERC Starting Grant from the European Research Council (ERC). From School to Career: Towards A Career Perspective on the Labor Market Returns to Education (CAREER) is a five-year research project (2021-2026), funded by the European Research Council. It aims to develop a better understanding of workers' employment trajectories in the context of changing labour markets.

Pew Research Center survey

Online resource Non formal

Pew Research Center survey on why more American students do not pursue STEM majors

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, Cluster 2 destination 3

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action partly aligns with the STEM strategy plans where it expands the scope of proposed action of identifying the underlying the pre-existing causes and motivation of students on how to attract them to STEM education through STEAM approaches (3.2 pg. 8, "better anticipating sector-specific skills needs as part of the future European Skills Intelligence Observatory and by leveraging the common European Data Space for Skills.)

Evidence: Holmegaard, et al. 2014 Mandalapu & Gnog, 2019 Wang, Ye & Degol, 2017 Tandrayen-Ragoobur & Gokulsing, 2022

EU University alliance on STEAM

Support the creation of a European Universities alliance on STEM and STEAM education.

Examples

CIVIS

Course Online resource University PhD

It is Europe's Civic University Alliance, bringing together a community of more than 470,000 students and 58,000 staff members. It is the fruit of the special collaboration between 11 leading research higher education institutions across Europe.

EU STEM coalition

Online resource Non formal

It is not focused specifically on universities but includes several typologies of European STEM and sTEM actors

Potential funding instrument

European University Initiative;
Erasmus+ and National funds

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the alliance of universities for STEM education along with the STEAM education (3.2, pg. 9 "Working towards a European degree for engineers, by building on the European Universities alliances and ongoing Erasmus+ pilots, considering the needs of employers.")

Related policy recommendations: [Coming soon]

Evidence: SEER D3.2 SEER D2.2

Update the Digital Education Plan to be more inclusive

Revise the Digital Education Plan ensuring that it covers all underrepresented groups to access digital education and a more complete definition of equity and inclusivity in addition to gender(s), to consider physical and mental disabilities, neurodivergence, diverse abilities, sensory needs, socio-economic background, mobility limitations, language and literacy competence. In particular, action 13 of the DEAP should be expanded to incorporate more diversity not just across the gender spectrum, but incorporating other identity lines such as race, disability and class in a truly intersectional approach. In this sense it is essential to ensure that learning materials for digital education are designed with a multiplicity of needs in mind, adopting a Design for All approach.

Equity is about the systemic or structural attention to giving everyone access to things in the right way for their needs. The shift to more inclusive practices should be reflected in KPIs and other targets, moving beyond a mere increase in the number or percentage of women (or other underrepresented groups) studying, working and doing business in digital and STEM fields, towards more comprehensive measures of inclusive representation, including at a minimum measures of diversity at all level of the organisation, within decision-making bodies, pay equity and chances of career advancement including diverse abilities and sensory needs, as well as (reduction in) cases of discrimination and harassment.

Potential funding instrument: Digital Education Plan

Suggested time frame: 2026

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 7

Evidence: in the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027 (DEAP), STEAM is mentioned in Action 13 as a way to increase women's participation in STEM studies and careers – just intended as an instrument to improve the outcomes of STEM education, without making fundamental changes

Díaz-García, C., González-Moreno, A., & Jose Sáez-Martínez, F. (2013) Carter et al., 2021

Capacity building in public administrations for multi-stakeholder collaborations and co-financing (open-schooling)

Multi-stakeholder collaborations through open-schooling, fuse the STEAM approach, open schooling environment and living lab practice within an empowering partnership based on local level collaboration between formal, non-formal and informal technology and science education providers, enterprises, local businesses, cultural institutions, and civil society (also called “STEAM Learning Ecologies”; ref. SENSE, SEER). Research should investigate how STEAM Learning Ecologies can sustain the implementation and cost of STEAM teaching and learning practices, and how it can foster a systemic change in the education system through multi-stakeholder collaborations. Schools and universities innovate their role – aligned with Europe vision of systemic change implemented in the EU Missions– which in enacted through a revised role of public institutions as enablers of systemic change by activating the local ecosystem, empowering trainers and learners to become themselves agents of change (SENSE). The investigation of the effectiveness of partnerships could include sharing or sponsoring spaces and equipment, as well as mentorship programmes to foster meaningful interaction between professionals, scientists, and students, ensuring that students gain insights into real-world applications of their learning. Partnerships should align educational outcomes with labour market needs and societal challenges, particularly in sectors requiring both technical and creative skills, such as digital innovation, design, and renewable energy, as well as considering top skills that can foster employment (i.e., Data Analysis and Interpretation; Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning; Cybersecurity; Cloud Computing; Programming and Software Development; Analytical/Mathematical Thinking; People Management and Leadership; Communication and Teamwork; Adaptability & Innovation; Technical Proficiency and IT Skills (SEER). Collaboration with industries and livinglabs can provide the necessary labs and materials for STEAM activities.

Examples

SALL

Project (Funded)

Toolkit

Primary

High School

Schools As Living Labs" (SALL) is a (project) that adapts open-schooling and Living Lab methodologies to create and test new tools for schools in 10 countries. It involves 412 school communities, aiming to support the design and implementation of living-lab activities, foster community-building, and promote sustainable open-schooling practices across Europe.

More examples: [\[Smithsonian Museum and Ukraine Ministry of Education and Science\]](#) [\[Polifactory: fablab of Politecnico di Milano\]](#)
[\[InChildHealth example of project\]](#) [\[Bosch-Stiftung Germany\]](#) [\[Politecnico di Milano: Festival dell'ingegneria\]](#)

OSOS

Model

Interactive tool

Primary

High School

The OSOS Open Schooling Model helps school leaders explore ways to transform schools into innovation hubs, enabling effective co-design and use of educational content, tools, and services for personalized science learning and teaching.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 all pillars and Missions, Cluster 3 EIT and EIE, and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action support the plan expanding it to STEAM (3.2 pg. 8, In 2025, “The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education”)

Related policy recommendations: [SENSE recommendation 2 & 4 \(SENSE D5.4\)](#) [Collaboration between Education and Industry \(SEER D3.2\)](#)

Evidence: [SENSE D5.5](#) [SEER D3.2](#) [STREAM-IT \(forthcoming\)](#) [Biagi, F \(2020\)](#)

STEAM career design

Longitudinal study to design and test support for STEAM career design and exploration across the learner's journey (cradle to grave) aligned with EU priorities (Green Deal, competitiveness, security, democracy) and job market needs. Define and test a replicable methodology for career exploration and life design with a focus on STEAM.

Examples

Designing Your Life

Program University PhD

Through this program, students are able to identify their ideal life and career, in collaboration with executive coaches and academic advisors to design an individualized, goal-driven pathway.

STEAMULE

Interactive tool Project (Funded) Formal

The STEAMULE project challenges career-related prejudices, such as gender stereotypes, to inspire young people to explore diverse career options. It encourages informed reflection on career choices through discussions. Additionally, the project supports educational teams by providing training in teaching practices and new skills, aligned with the Pact for Teaching Excellence and polytechnic education goals.

STEAMiE

Interactive tool Primary Middle High school Formal

An educational game engine developed by Ohio University to expose middle school students to science career fields.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 + FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan.

Evidence: Road-STEAMer D7.4

An economic case for *inclusive* STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education

Calculate the economic case of increasing STEAM education at secondary and tertiary level to provide evidence for policy making, and specifically the economic case for developing learning paths and environment that are inclusive for underrepresented groups, including women and all genders, people with disabilities, autism, ADHD, sensory sensitivity, low socio-economic status, migration background, etc., in partnership with industry players and other organizations. A longitudinal study (control trial) can inform future policies on the economic advantages of developing tailored skills development and career support for STEAM experts that are otherwise unemployed or underemployed because of vulnerabilities.

Examples

Learning programs suitable for twice-exceptional students

Centre

Formal

Bridges Academy is a leading school for gifted and twice-exceptional students (2e). Our students have an individual mix of high abilities and learning challenges.

LiNC-IT

Program

Formal

employment program that collaborates with government, nonprofits, and employers to provide employment opportunities for individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder

Companies and programs with inclusive culture and programs

Auticon

Microsoft's Neurodiversity Hiring Program

SAP's Autism at Work

IBM's Neurodiversity Advancement Initiative

Google Autism Career Program in collaboration with the Stanford Neurodiversity Project

Specialisterne

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 destination "Innovative Research on Social and Economic Transformations"

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the plan to broaden its impact on under-represented and marginalized group and increase employability.

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: SEER D3.1 Perales & Aróstegui, 2024 OECD Learning Compass for Mathematics

STEAM cradle to grave

Improving the connections from early years (EY) through primary upwards and beyond tertiary in STEAM education to provide a coherent progression for learners from kindergarten to retirement. More research is needed in STEAM practices for secondary and tertiary education and the linkages between educational levels, including continuous learning and upskilling. Learning from successful STE(A)M in primary education could be investigated at vocational training, secondary education and universities.

Examples

River as a learning & teaching space - Educational Transition Guide

Project (Funded)

Horizon Europe call “Effective education and labour market transitions of young people”

Project (Funded)

EU Pact for Skills

EU micro-credentials

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, Erasmus++

Suggested time frame: FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns and expands the STEM Education Strategic Plan

Related policy recommendations: SENSE recommendation 2 & 5, D5.5 SENSE D6.4

Evidence: Tytler et al. 2008 Nugent, et al. 2015 Shaby, et al. 2021

Training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM

Development and testing of training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM and related actions such as the effect of a "STEAM coordinator" or STEAM specialist in each school or university

Examples

Innovative Leaders Institute

Program

Formal

The Innovative Leaders Institute is a year-long program designed for school leaders aiming to transform current practices and bring high-quality STEM education to their students.

Purdue Polytechnic Institute

Program

University

Master of Science in Technology Leadership and Innovation with a focus on STEM Education Leadership. Graduates of the STEM Education Leadership program are prepared to become leaders in integrated STEM in a variety of positions including university professors, K-12 teachers, policymakers, administrators, informal learning specialists, and others. Participants learn to conduct research that informs practice.

McDaniel College STEM Instructional Leader

Program

University

This graduate certificate program aimed at preparing educators to take on STEM leadership roles within their schools and districts. The program is delivered online, consisting of 18 credits, and focuses on equipping participants with the skills necessary to make a significant impact in STEM education.

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

More examples: [Navigate EdTech – Choosing Wisely for Learners](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

this action expands the plan Alignment with the JRC Science for Policy Brief "STEM and STEAM education, and disciplinary integration: a guide to informed policy action": "Whole school approaches "imply collective and collaborative action in and by a school community to improve student learning, behaviour and well-being, and the conditions that support these"[27] by engaging the local community, school leaders, middle management, teaching and non-teaching staff, learners, parents, and families." (pg. 5)

Related policy recommendations: to be developed

Evidence: [Douthit, 2021](#); [Abbas et al. 2024](#); [SEER 2.3 \(2.3 pg. 15\)](#) [SEER focus group 7 \(pg. 6\)](#) [SEER D7.2 \(pg. 14\)](#)

Joint diplomas, degrees, microcredentials with industry/civic organizations - fast track recognition at EU level

Map and investigate best practices of joint programs between secondary/tertiary education providers with companies and/or civic organizations, in providing technical, agile and solid education aligned with market developments, credited by educational institutions and partially funded by companies and organizations. Investigate how educational institutions can effectively become facilitators of the establishment of academic programs that are co-designed with – and co-funded by - industrial and societal players that guarantee national and EU learning standards for credited education, including EU microcredentials for life long learning.

Examples

China fast-tracking university majors in weeks

Secondary education level:

IB Career-related Programme

Program High school

Education framework for students aged 16-19, combining academic study with career-focused learning, including traditional courses, career-related studies, personal and professional skills development.

More examples:

Alfa Academy school-industry partnership

STEAMhouse

Tertiary education level:

Vocational tertiary education (Universities of Applied Sciences /Fachhochschule/ Haute Ecole Spécialisée /ITS joint programs with industries

Applied tertiary education in joint programs with industry and non-commercial partners. Examples:

ITS Academy Machina Lonati (Italy), provides tertiary vocational education in STEAM (es. fashion tech). ITS programs are recognized across Europe as vocational tertiary education. Tertiary Formal

ITS Feralpi (Italy) paid a full salary to students to learn steel industry management. Tertiary Formal

Universities: Tertiary Formal

Double degrees, such as Politecnico di Milano Double degree in Management Engineering and Product Service System Design

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the STEM strategy plan to design effective joint programs and microcredentials collaborating with educational institutions, businesses and industries. (3.2 pg. 10, “ i) boost the available range of joint programmes and microcredentials in STEM, including with a STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) educational approach”)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: SEER D3.1 SEER D3.2

Investigation of what the arts, design and creativity bring to STEAM education and derive best practices

Triangulate literature with bottom-up evidence of which contribution and under which conditions the arts and design bring effective benefits to STEAM education, including mental health and career readiness, in order and derive best practices of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary education along the educational continuum (primary school to lifelong learning) within the European context. Investigate how strengthening the arts element in STEAM is helpful in trauma-conscious education, in which art can serve as a healing tool for traumatized or struggling students and to help teachers of STEM subjects to recognize art's relevance.

Examples

Cultural Learning Alliance Project

Project Primary Middle School

Is an activity, where Eastbourne's STEAM project used art and science to explore plastic pollution through photography, sculpture, journaling, graphic design, and culminating in a public exhibition

More examples: Arts at CERN CREAM digital art project Particle Physics and the visual arts EASE Quantum Visions Vertigo S+T+Arts

Creation features

Program Primary Middle School

This is a STEAM-based **program**, an experiential learning approach that fosters curiosity, resilience, and leadership, ensuring students build knowledge progressively and develop essential life skills

Potential funding instrument

Horizon, Pillar 2 and WIDERA

Suggested time frame 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action supports and expands the plan advocating a stronger focus on the STEAM approach that supports holistic learning, curriculum design, that can be applied to create "Joint transnational programmes and short courses" in more informed STEAM approach. (3.2, pg. 10 "Develop joint transnational programmes and short courses leading to microcredentials in strategic STEM sectors, as identified in the Competitiveness Compass, through the Centres of Vocational Excellence and European Universities alliances. In close cooperation with their respective innovation ecosystems and with EU skills academies: i) boost the available range of joint programmes and microcredentials in STEM, including with a STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) educational approach

Related policy recommendations: RoadSTEAMer Recommendation 1 (D3.3)

Evidence: SENSE D3.2 (4.1 pg. 29) Road-STEAMer D3.1 Road-STEAMer D2.2 Penprase, B.E. (2018) Pirrie, A. (2019) Road-STEAMer-D2.2 Road-STEAMer-D4.1 STEM Competencies, Challenges, and Measurements, Biagi F.

Deployment and investigation of new approach to teachers' training (pre-service and in-service) for transdisciplinary education (pre-service and in-service): STEM competence framework for educators and school leaders

Development and application of transdisciplinary, project-based, student-focused STEAM frameworks, such as the STEAMComp Edu, possibly aligned with the ESCO classification, for training educators in Europe, at all educational levels. Research is needed to investigate the effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary education frameworks in increasing teachers/lecturers, school heads, students and schools' proficiency in breaking silos when teaching STEAM subjects, fostering interdisciplinary, trainers' inclusive attitude and ability to collaborate among teachers, engage students and local actors. Include a multi-level governance component, addressing national training institutions (to be considered as multipliers) to adapt EU resources to specific contexts using tailored teachers training for collaborative project-based mindset, supported by content and tools.

Examples

STEAMComp Edu

Framework

Formal

Non-formal

It is a framework that focuses on developing the competencies needed to design and implement effective STEAM education. The framework primarily supports educators in creating inclusive, engaging, and innovative learning experiences for students.

Still I rise educational approach

Formal

The humanitarian organization was nominated to the Nobel peace prize in 2023 for providing world-class education in vulnerable contexts. Teachers training include emotional intelligence, "critical and creative thinking, instilling deep passion and a concrete commitment to social justice and societal progress."

More examples: [\[steamonedu\]](#) [LUMA Centre](#)

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

Aligns with the STEM competence framework which should be enlarged to STEAM holistic competence (3.2 pg. 9 "Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills.")

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 3 D3.3

Evidence: [SEER D2.2 \(3 pg. 27\)](#), [Spyropoulou & Kameas, 2023](#) [Oanh, 2025](#)

Research on STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment to investigate and test best practices

Building on the action “systematic organization of open-access STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment, identification of gaps and development in all EU languages with feedback loops for improvement”, systematic assessment and data collection (potentially a monitoring tool) on the use of STEAM teaching material and practices to derive the most effective practices in diverse contexts and for diverse learners’ profiles. Specific research should be conducted on teachers/lecturer ability and compliance and encountered challenges for large scale implementation of the STEAM approach in government educational institutions, including methodologies to finance labs and STEAM resources and materials

Examples

STEAMonEdu MOOC

Project

Framework

The project aims to boost STE(A)M education by supporting educators' professional development through blended training and an online community. It will create a STE(A)M education framework, including curricula, competencies, and policies. The project also offers a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) for educators, guides on best practices, and tools for STE(A)M policy influencers, focusing on diversity and competence development.

STEAM Hub Leadership Programme (UK)

Program

Primary

Middle

High School

The STEAM Hub Leadership Programme empowers teachers to design STEAM curricula and build industry partnerships while equipping diverse young people with skills for STEAM careers. It fosters an inclusive STEAM community in Camden, influencing policy and regional growth.

Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

More examples: [SpicE MOOC](#) [eTwinning](#) [ETH Zurich](#) [Cream project](#) [Circular STEM](#)

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2

Suggested time frame: FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It can expand the European STEM Executive Panel to include the STEAM approach (3.2 pg. 8 encourage the centres and alliances to coordinate their STEM offer and to pool and share their investments in STEM infrastructure, equipment, and educational technologies.)

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 2](#)

Evidence: [SEER, Focus group 7](#) [Road-STEAMer D2.3](#) [Road-STEAMer-D2.2](#) [Road-STEAMer-D4.1](#)

[Supporting Teachers to Foster Creativity and Critical Thinking: Cassie Hague](#)

Development of networks, centres and alliances (incl. equipment) of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for mutual learning on STEAM

Development of networks of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for hybrid (face-to-face and online training) mutual learning on STEAM curriculum and STEAM schools/universities., through both physical and digital collaborative environments, for example through twinning programs, teachers exchanges, MOOCs and face-to-face events for peer-to-peer learning, to promote knowledge exchange and the dissemination of successful STEAM practices.

Examples

Scientix

Online resource

Formal

It is the STEM Education Community in Europe. It offers the space for all people working in the field of science education to exchange, collaborate and learn from each other. It includes the STEM Alliance, a platform for STEM educators and companies

EASE – EuropeAn Network of STEAM Educators

Online resource

Primary

Middle

A non-profit organization that aims at enhancing the work of all educators and teachers in terms of promoting STEAM skills with children, young people and adults in formal and non-formal education.

PHERECLOS project

Project (Funded)

Primary

Middle

High School

A Horizon project, building upon the experience of Children's Universities (CUs) in Europe and beyond. Due to their engagement with children and young people, they help to break down institutional boundaries between universities and the wider society, focusing on open schooling. STEAM education is highlighted. The project developed a complete teacher training toolkit. There is also a collection of good practices.

More examples:

STEAMonEdu MOOC

School As living Labs (SALL EU project)

[ArtsWork creating seven STEAM networks in SE England]

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It expands by including a STEAM focus on the creation of centres and alliances, that could be focused on specific sub-sectors of STEM (3.2 pg. 10 D ii. encourage the centres and alliances to coordinate their STEM offer and to pool and share their investments in STEM infrastructure, equipment and educational technologies.)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 4, D3.3

Evidence: SEER D3.2

EU Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum / school / university and assessment

From existing cases and scientific evidence of STEAM holistic curriculum and STEAM schools and universities, co-create with learners, lecturers and all stakeholders a pan-European definition and assessment that aligned with EU priorities (including digital education) and can be adaptable to national educational systems, identifying gaps and overlaps across EU MS and their alignment with EU priorities. This research action should also define indicators, collecting data and monitoring

Examples

Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

Framework

Penryn College, Cornwall UK

Curriculum

Middle School

STEAM **curriculum** embedded in an arts/science rich college in which the learner's journey is mapped through various stages ensuring character build and career build are developed simultaneously through each step

Centre for Research in Transdisciplinary Education

Research Center

This new Centre (est 2025) offers fertile dialogic ground to breed innovative ideas in educational research within and between subject disciplines. It draws on, and develops, new methodologies from arts-based, creative and post-qualitative methods through to exploratory quantitative approaches, working with STEAM and transdisciplinary educational practice and researching with community and industry partners

Nansledan School

Program

Primary School

This is a STEAM-based **program**, an experiential learning approach that fosters curiosity, resilience, and leadership, ensuring students build knowledge progressively and develop essential life skills

STEM School label

Strategy

A STEM School is defined as a school with a clear STEM strategy, characterised by different key elements and criteria. This definition is the result of the European STEM Schools Report which builds upon a vast literature review and a thorough consultation process with four groups of key stakeholders in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education. Those key stakeholders are schools, STEM teachers, Ministries of Education and STEM Industries. The report's criteria for "STEM Schools" identify key areas that can help schools advance and have a clearer strategy for STEM education (funded by the H2020 project Scientix 4 Grant agreement N. 101000063, coordinated by European Schoolnet EUN)

More Example: [International Experiential School](#)

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe, Pillar 2, Cluster 2 "Culture, Creativity and inclusive society", destination "innovative research on social and economic transformation"

Suggested time frame 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns and enhances the plan for a pan-European STEM competence framework, including holistic curricula design for STEM skill competencies. This will also add an inclusive lens to assess STEM skills (3.2, pg. 9 "Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills")

Related policy recommendations: [RoadSTEAMer Recommendation 1 \(D3.3\)](#) [SEER D7.2](#)

Evidence: [Road-STEAMer-D2.3](#) [Watts, D. S. and Richardson, J. W. \(2020\)](#) [SEER D7.2](#) [Road-STEAMer-D2.2](#) [Road-STEAMer-D4.1](#)
[Transdisciplinary education and innovation through STEAM, Carter, C.](#)

Increase STEAM teaching prestige through fostering schools/university collaborations with local actors

Increase STEAM teaching prestige through fostering structured schools/university collaborations with local actors (industry players, SMEs, civic organizations, governmental institutions) to equip educators with practical knowledge that they can transfer into the classroom and increase the school/university reputation. Develop best practices and investigate the impact of collaborations on teachers/lecturers perceived self-efficacy and reputation.

Examples

School As living Labs (SALL EU project)

Project (Funded) Primary Secondary

Schools As Living Labs" (SALL) is a project that adapts open-schooling and Living Lab methodologies to create and test new tools for schools in 10 countries. It involves 412 school communities, aiming to support the design and implementation of living-lab activities, foster community-building, and promote sustainable open-schooling practices across Europe.

SATO

Program Primary Secondary

The Schools Across the Ocean program, developed by the University of Exeter, Emirates Literature Foundation, and Khorfakkan University, helps teachers address climate education. Involving 14 schools in the UK and UAE, it engages 400 children to explore ocean-related issues using a specially designed toolkit, fostering community connections and action.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe or Erasmus+

More examples: [\[SciCultureD\]](#) [\[EFPM839 Transdisciplinary Collaborations for Creative Futures\]](#) [Teach For All](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

Aligns with the European STEM Executive Panel development (3.2 pg. 8, "to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education"; "Supported by Erasmus+, these centres will create dynamic learning ecosystems that drive innovation in STEM teaching and learning in schools, by stepping up cooperation with businesses, science museums, STEM organisations, libraries, cultural associations, creative industries, universities and research institutions")

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 4, D3.3](#)

Evidence: [SEER D2.2 \(3.2\)](#)

Mentorship programs and scholarships for underrepresented groups

Research the effectiveness of implementing targeted interventions for vulnerable and underrepresented students in STEAM, such as mentorship programs, peer to peer buddy programs, scholarships, access to a range of educational options and approaches (including part-time and micro-credentials) that can support a variety of their needs such as reduced mobility to diverse abilities, safety, religion or cost, sensory issues, anxiety, neurodiversity, and socio-economic status.

Examples

Schools and Universities support programs

Stepchange: mentally healthy universities framework of UniversitiesUK (whole university approach)

Framework University

Politecnico di Milano program for students with diverse abilities

Resources, mentorship, and networking

Primary - High School University Non formal Initiative

Latinas in STEM empowers Latina women in STEM fields by offering resources, mentorship, and networking opportunities to support their success in education and careers

Scholarships (from sponsors)

University Non formal Formal Initiative

Google's Women Techmakers offers scholarships programs to women in computer science and related fields, providing financial support, mentorship, and networking opportunities.

MESA Community support program for disadvantaged students

Middle High School University Initiative

Mathematics, Engineering, Science Achievement (MESA) is an academic preparation program for pre-college, community college and university-level students. Established in 1970 in California, the program provides academic support to students from educationally disadvantaged backgrounds throughout the education pathway so they will excel in math and science and ultimately attain four-year degrees in science, technology, engineering or math (STEM) fields. MESA has been named among the top five most innovative public programs in the USA: an initiative of the Ford Foundation, the Kennedy School of Government at Harvard University, and the Council for Excellence in Government

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action does not align with STEM strategy plan, but it can expand by including vulnerable and under-represented groups to their mentorship program along with scholarship that can improve the attractiveness to STEM careers and education.

Related policy recommendations: While gender diversity remains critical, future policies should adopt a more comprehensive approach to inclusion in STEAM education, addressing barriers faced by ethnic minorities, low-income students, and students with disabilities providing access to a range of educational options and approaches that can cater the variety of their needs, and provide funding to monitor the effectiveness of those measures. **Road-STEAMer recommendation 8 D3.3**

Evidence: Tandrayen-Ragoobur & Gokulsing, 2022 **The_SEER_FocusGroup05 SENSE D6.1 SEER D3.2**

STEAM entrepreneurship education

Research should be funded to investigate how to foster entrepreneurship in STEAM through secondary and tertiary programs, for example developing highschool programs and university degrees focused on supporting learners to develop their own businesses, as well as experimenting with microfunding and networks with SMEs and businesses

Examples

BUILD program

Program Middle High school

entrepreneurship programs from few hours to 3 years, embedded in The school program (USA)

Switzerland Venture program

Program University Non formal

the state-financed start-up programs, competition and funds are potentially recognized as college credits and promoted in universities with a focus on technological startups

High School Entrepreneurship

Program High School

program at Berkley university: 2 week program for 50 students per year supported to develop a business plan at the University campus

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 3 EIT and EIE

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the plan: "Provide dedicated training on innovation, entrepreneurship and IP management to 200 000 STEM higher education students, academics and staff by 2028, building on the EIT Higher Education Institutions Initiative in synergy with the European Universities alliances and the EIT knowledge and innovation communities." (pg. 10)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: Poggesi et al., 2020

“Mission Education” - Systemic change of the educational system and assessment by orchestrating STEM/STEAM education research actions of EU funded projects for enhancing EU competitiveness through monitoring and scaling of actions for skills development, harnessing AI and digital technologies through a transdisciplinary inclusive approach to learning

Develop a Mission for the systemic innovation of EU education with the aim to orchestrate long-term systemic innovation for transdisciplinary inclusive technical education in the EU, through testing an EU curriculum and standardized testing, to inform and work in close coordination with the upcoming “European STEM executive Panel” and the European skills high level board (STEM Education Strategic Plan pg. 8) and European Skills Intelligence Observatory, to support the development of the STEM Education Strategic Plan’s goal of “Improve overall STEM skills intelligence based on international indicators and benchmarks, by measuring graduate outcomes in VET and tertiary education” (pg.8). Such program could overcome the “fragmentation of resources across programs” (pg. 12). It would coordinate EU funded research projects, collecting and analyzing qualitative and quantitative longitudinal data at every level (student, teacher, school, region, countries) to complement PISA assessment with more granular data, for the deployment and testing of digital education and AI in all educational levels, to scale existing successful projects and boost the opportunities that it provides for flexible (hybrid, blended, online) and inclusive (customized) skills-based STEAM education opportunities for vulnerable groups and learners with diverse abilities. It can be structured as the EU Missions (Cities, Adaptation, Soil, Ocean and Cancer), mobilizing systemic change through long-term (7-10 years) coordination of actions within and between European countries (as the National platforms in the Mission “Cities” and the “deep dives” of the Mission “Adaptation”) to deploy and investigate a step-by-step progressive pathway toward project-based, transdisciplinary, AI-enhanced transdisciplinary (challenge-based or phenomenon-based) education in line with EU priorities. The Mission Education should coordinate the definition of mixed methods, process and outcome indicators and sensemaking processes, collecting data and monitoring step-by-step progressive pathways of STEM and STEAM practices (beyond disciplinary silos), programs, schools and universities in the EU - assessing beyond knowledge also life skills and mental health/wellbeing- to inform policy making for evidence-based educational reforms.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and inclusive society; destination: “Innovative Research on Societal and Economic Transformation”) and cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and space); Erasmus

Examples: [EU Missions](#) [Mission Cities](#) [Mission Adaptation](#) [Impact pathways in the Mission Cities](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 + FP10 2028-34 (longitudinal action 7 to 10 years)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the STEM Strategic Plan to propose the creation of a long-term research action to orchestrate systemic innovation in EU education, supporting the Union of Skills, to support the EU in achieving the goal of Improve overall STEM skills intelligence based on international indicators and benchmarks (pg.8).

STEM skills intelligence

Improve overall STEM skills intelligence based on international indicators and benchmarks, by measuring graduate outcomes in VET and tertiary education through the Eurograduate survey, and by better anticipating sector-specific skills needs as part of the future European Skills Intelligence Observatory and by leveraging the common European Data Space for Skills.

Evidence: [Mazzuccato 2018](#) [Mazzuccato 2021](#) [Pokropek, 2025](#)

Learning Environment design and its impact on learning outcomes

Research on the physical environment impact on educational outcomes for a variety of students' needs and abilities (including disabilities) to design STEAM spaces that consider the overall quality of the learning experience alongside functionality, and promoting participatory, reflective design strategies that create spaces reflecting the views and feelings of all participants. The traditional classroom is a “symbol” for a particular educational approach; a STEAM space is essentially a “not-a-classroom” space (SENSE) that can include labs, outdoor learning and learning through experiences with the school/university community. Investigate diverse pathways into science education through inclusive spaces, by creating platforms and opportunities for students and the school community to contribute to the design of learning environments. Research to provide evidence-based design of inclusive learning environments that are suitable for learners and lecturers with high sensory sensitivity or other needs (moving, privacy, rest, sensory rooms, labs) and its relation to making spaces accessible to everyone (SENSE), supporting wellbeing for all, through a positive impact on mental health, which should then be included into teachers training (pre-service and on-service).

Examples

Labs

Centre Middle High School

UCL Academy is a specialist school emphasizing a STEAM-focused curriculum. The school offers specialized facilities, including science laboratories, engineering suites, and performance spaces, to support its interdisciplinary approach to education

More examples: SPICE academy STEAM.SENSE lab Odyssea

OTTER

Project (Funded)

Primary-High School Formal

an Erasmus+ project on learning outside the classroom, specifically to improve scientific knowledge, get closer to STEAM subjects. It provides toolkits and guidelines practitioners can use to teach outside the classroom.

SENSE project Deliverables

[D5.1 Scoping report on STEAM spaces](#)

[D5.2. Report on Evaluation of space strategies for the STEAM Roadmap](#)

[D5.3 Self-experimentation toolkits and design principles for STEAM spaces](#)

[D5.4 Policy recommendations: STEAM spaces and the New European Bauhaus](#)

Sensory and Quiet rooms

Education institutions have sensory rooms or quiet rooms to be used for meltdown prevention

Universal Design

Design for All

Outdoor learning

Examples:

The Green School in Bali

UBC MOOC on STEM Outside

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to promote more inclusive learning to increase the uptake of STEM education.

Related policy recommendations: SENSE recommendation 1, D5.4

Evidence: SENSE D5.1 SENSE D5.4 Aron, 2002 McAllister, 2010 Byers, Terry, Wesley Imms, and Elizabeth Hartnell-Young. 2014 Pluess, 2019 Butera, et al., 2020 Rose, 2000

Funding for EDTECH startups to promote STEAM

Fund EU start-ups to promote STEAM education, modular learning materials with online training for educators, harnessing AI for students customized online learning, potentially online educational activities with students across EU Member states.

Examples

AI learning apps for educators

Online resource University

Brian AI teaching assistant is a gamified learning app for all educators established in Switzerland and utilized by the University of St. Gallen

More example:

Khan Academy

Edtech programs

Program Middle School

Girls code it better is a 45h free program for girls at school, one afternoon a week at schools

Arduino

Online resource Middle High School

University

Used by over 50,000 schools and universities, Arduino Education offers open-source STEAM tools for learning electronics, programming, IoT, and robotics from middle school to university. It's taught at top institutions like MIT and widely used in high school STEM programs, especially in robotics clubs and science fairs. In Italy, it's integrated into national curricula for technology and engineering.

Potential funding instrument

Pillar 3 (i.e., EIT digital transformation)

Suggested time frame: FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It expands the STEM strategic plan and aligns with EU priority of entrepreneurship.

Example categorization

Type of Education:

- Curriculum/Program
- Project (funded)
- Initiative
- Online Resource
- Course/Activity
- Teachers/lecturer training
- Interactive tool/toolkit
- Model/Framework

Level of Education:

- Primary school
- Middle school
- High School
- University/tertiary
- Phd
- formal/non-formal
- Centre/Institute

STEAM career exploration centers

Experiment and test the co-creation of career exploration centers that students can attend from the last year of middle school to university, substituting a part of class hours, to promote authentic transdisciplinary learning, an informed understanding of career options and experiences, focused on careers in high demand and in relation to EU priorities (i.e, the Green Deal, cybersecurity, entrepreneurship, etc.). The centers can offer structured activities between secondary and tertiary education, or teachers/university lecturers training on career design support to students, which are investigated through longitudinal studies to co-design and test the effectiveness in particular for vulnerable students. The centers promote lifelong learning beyond the traditional school years and encourage inclusion of local actors, in collaboration with businesses that co-finance the centers.

Examples

Gereau Center for Applied Technology and Career Exploration

Centre Middle School

At the Gereau Center, career exploration is integrated into the eighth-grade (curriculum) through project-based learning, specialized courses, and hands-on experiences. Students explore fields like engineering, design, and medical studies while working on real-world projects. They engage with industry professionals, use applied technology, and develop critical thinking skills.

More examples: Amazon future engineer BECOME

Career Exploration in high school

Program High School

whole or half year option, students experience up to 8 different career programs, for 5 weeks each. It is a public program provided in 4 locations by the US Board of Cooperative Educational Services (BOCES) of ERIE 1 (19 school districts of NY State)

Explore STEM and pathways to STEM

Program Primary Middle High School

extra-curricular programs offered by a private educational travel America company that provides n20 different career, leadership, and technology programs that take place in cities across the United States and the world part of the WorldStrides company.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan, in particular the "STEM skills foundries" centres through which students experience and explore in-demand STEM career option in relation to EU priorities with the inclusion of local actors and take informed career choices. (3.2 pg. 10, "Pilot in 2026 the development of STEM skills foundries in strategic sectors by involving companies to mentor young student entrepreneurs, in cooperation with vocational education and training providers and with higher education institutions, providing them access to their laboratories, technical infrastructures and equipment, development of intellectual property (IP), as well as facilitating access to venture capital. This should also bring together VET and higher education providers, talented VET and higher education students and the world of finance, particularly venture capital"

Related policy recommendations: SENSE

Evidence: Visher et al., 2013

Doctoral network on STEAM

Develop doctoral networks across universities and with industry partners to promote STEAM competence of PhD candidates and research on STEAM effectiveness, including strong monitoring skills and knowledge of randomized control trials

Examples

STEP CHANGE

Program PhD

Interdisciplinary doctoral program at Politecnico di Milano is a cross-departmental doctoral program in Science, Technology, and Policy for Sustainable Change, hosted at the Electronic Engineering department, focused on sustainability and policy implications of technical research

CoDesign4Transitions

Program PhD

A Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Networks programme. The doctoral researchers carry out new research and develop skills at the intersection of co-design, sustainability, service and systems design, democratic innovation, and climate transitions

J-PAL policy action lab

Online resource University

Provides training in conducting and evaluation randomized control trials

Potential funding instrument

Marie Skłodowska-Curie joint and industrial doctorates

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the plan (pg.4)

EU Council of societal challenges to introduce a challenge on education

EU Council of societal challenges is advised to introduce a challenge on education and/or embed transversally education in all challenges, i.e., transdisciplinary STEAM approaches to support the climate emergency and STEAM focus on arts and skills-based open schooling approach to support mental health.

We advocate for the stronger integration of education—school education, teacher training, and tertiary education—into the European research and innovation (R&I) agenda, in response to the Expert Group's Align, Act, Accelerate Recommendation 7. This is an opportunity to enhance the existing collaborative framework between universities, research institutions, governments, civil society, and industry by explicitly recognising education as a driver of innovation, resilience, and societal transformation. Emphasising methodologies such as Open Schooling, STEAM education, Living Labs, Co-design, and Informal and Non-formal Learning, we call for dedicated funding, governance inclusion, support for transdisciplinary ecosystems, and investment in teacher capacity. Education is positioned not merely as preparatory but as an active co-creator of knowledge-based, human-centred solutions to complex societal challenges, contributing to a more inclusive, sustainable, and secure European future.

Examples

Schools as Living Labs

Project

Primary

Middle

High School

Living Labs are open-innovation spaces where students, schools, citizens, and organizations co-create STEAM-based solutions to real-world problems. The SALL project tested this approach in 400+ schools, showing strong results: 77% of teachers reported improved student independence and problem-solving, while 78% noted enhanced professional development in project-based learning and open schooling.

Make it Open

Project

Framework

Primary

Middle School

Empowering schools to act as drivers of community well-being by building synergies between educational institutions, enterprises, and civil society organisations. The project facilitated the co-design and implementation of activities in which students addressed real-life local challenges in partnership with their communities. Drawing on tools and methodologies from the maker movement, the initiative promoted hands-on, inquiry-based learning while strengthening schools' roles as hubs of social innovation and local engagement.

Potential funding instrument

EU council of societal challenges

Suggested time frame: FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025 This action expands the plan

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 5 D3.3

Evidence: SENSE D4.3

The new role of education/teachers/lecturers in an AI-enhanced STEAM education and work environment: arts for fostering equality and wellbeing

Research is needed to investigate the potential of AI to support customized education, in coordination with studies (funded by other calls/DGs) on changing requirements in workers' AI skills and changing role of skills needed by citizens (children and adults) due to AI development, including a critical appraisal of AI and its environmental, social and economic impact. Studies should consider effective development of students' skills in critical thinking, coping with information overload and complexity, with the aim to test how AI can be most effectively deployed in education for increasing inclusion of learners with a broad range of needs (neurodivergence, socio-economic background, sensory sensitivity, genders) and paying attention to mental health (anxiety) and AI support in students' self-evaluation.

Examples

IN-STEAM

A training course for educators of the school sector will be implemented and delivered focused on the ELP method, its applications for inclusion and the exploitation of Artificial Intelligence in teaching STEAM.

More examples: [STEM learning resources on AI](#) [STEAMBRACE project](#) [STREAM IT project](#) [Alpha AI powered school](#) [AI Empowerment in STEM Education](#)

CONNECT

A course, part of the Erasmus teacher training program, aims to bridge the gap between artificial intelligence (AI) advancements and classroom application, specifically designed for educators across Europe

CIVIS AI and STEAM

A comprehensive initiative for students (2025) that integrates AI into STEAM education through physical and virtual learning experiences

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and space) and cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and inclusive society; destination: "Innovative Research on Societal and Economic Transformation")

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action partially aligns with the STEM Strategy Plan by contributing to the European STEM Executive Panel's role in designing industry-relevant curricula and developing the STEM Competence Framework using the ESCO classification. It further expands the plan by emphasizing the need to address how digital tools and AI enable to address diverse learner needs, including those related to neurodivergence, mental health, etc through STEAM practices, resulting in a more inclusive and holistic framework. (3.2 pg. 8 I and 9 "Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills.")

Related policy recommendations: [SEER D7.2](#)

Evidence: [Xu & Ouyang, 2022](#) [Kohnke & Zaugg, 2025](#) [Park & Kwon, 2024](#) [SEER D3.2](#)

Deployment and investigation of education and training through citizen science applied to STEAM

Identification and co-design of citizen science projects applied to STEAM, design and deployment of open science and citizen science projects for STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education, to investigate the effectiveness of citizen science as a learning practice, as well as providing data to current research (i.e., aligned with societal grand challenges), including more than human approaches

Examples

Malta Science in the City

Activity

Non-formal

Malta Science in the City is an Activity based on an annual festival that blends science, art, and innovation, encouraging public engagement through interactive exhibits, performances, and workshops emphasizing on Citizen Science, inviting the public to actively participate in scientific research and contribute to data collection. The event is part of the European Researchers' Night, helping bridge the gap between science and society.

National Geographic Citizen Science projects

Project

Non-formal

Citizen science projects where volunteers help collect data for scientific research. These projects span various fields, including ecology and space, allowing individuals to contribute to real-world scientific discoveries. Participants can engage in activities like wildlife monitoring, weather observation, and environmental tracking.

SENSE project report on the Citizen Science and Art-Practices Workshop - Deliverable 3.2

Other projects MOST (Meaningful Open Schooling Connects Schools To Communities) Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

Potential funding instrument

Pillar 2 Cluster 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan

Related policy recommendations: SENSE recommendation 2, Policy-Brief-RP1-V1

Evidence: Road-STEAMer D3.1 Vohland et al. 2021 SENSE D3.4 Sauermann, H. et al. (2020) Road-STEAMer-D2.2 Road-STEAMer-D4.1

*In 2025, set up a **European STEM Executive Panel** at top business/ political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the **European Skills High Level Board** and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party.*

Integrate STEAM education in Horizon Europe Pillar 2 calls, in particular Cluster 2

Integrating STEAM education into the Green Deal initiatives to provide students (especially in secondary and tertiary education) with the interdisciplinary skills needed to address complex issues like climate change. STEAM education should explicitly promote critical thinking and the ability to reflect on the ethical, political, and societal dimensions of technology and design, recognising that these are not neutral.

Examples

HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-11

Project (Funded)

Non formal

The HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-11 is a funding opportunity under the Horizon Europe program, aimed at using arts and creative sectors to engage the public in protecting and restoring aquatic environments. Projects are encouraged to collaborate with the Creative Europe program and align with the New European Bauhaus initiatives, particularly in coastal and maritime regions.

More examples: [PREPSOIL Project \(Mission Soil\)](#)

LOESS Project (Mission Soil)

Project (Funded)

Primary

Middle

High School

Non formal

hands-on soil education through community-engaged research and learning, including activities tailored for schools to foster practical understanding of soil-related issues and the “Mooc soil education: an integrated stem approach”

Neuroclima (Mission Adaptation)

Project (Funded)

Toolkit

Non formal

the project will deliver three toolkits for stakeholders and citizens for the green transition towards combating climate change: (1) participatory design, (2) creative writing and (3) cinematography, animation, and performing arts. These toolkits foster inclusive and widespread participation, educate citizens of all ages, developing essential skills among educators, policymakers, decision-makers, and others in public governance to educate citizens about climate-related initiatives, gather feedback, and promote innovative participatory policy co-design.

Potential funding instrument

Embed STEAM and industry/societal needs in Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2 destination 3 calls on education

Suggested time frame: 26-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to leverage existing funding instruments

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 5](#) [SENSE recommendation 5](#)

Evidence: [SEER D3.2](#) [Cedefop \(2023c\)](#)

Systematic organization of open-access STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment, identification of gaps and development in all EU languages with feedback loops for improvement

STEAM material mapping, systematic organization, identification of gaps and development of open educational resources (including modules to be integrated into courses as well as holistic STEAM curricula) to be provided in a user-friendly platform, co-created with teachers and lecturers of diverse educational levels, organized by relevant variables (educational level, language, disciplines, time, inclusivity level, etc.). These materials should prioritise pedagogical relevance, ensuring they are meaningful rather than solely engaging or performative and based on real-life challenges and skills development (instead of knowledge-centred education), according for example to the EU “Lifecomp” and related to a range of careers exploration (in collaboration with external stakeholders including companies and governmental organizations). Starting by gathering already existing resources and making them accessible (in different languages) currently under-utilised resources from previous projects, including EU-funded initiatives, should be systematized in a one-stop-shop digital space where lecturers can easily find materials, share, find peer-to-peer support and provide feedback on pedagogical effectiveness and evidence from assessment that takes into account AI implications for learning and assessment.

Examples

Roadsteamer map of STEAM practices in Europe

Project Online resource

Scientix

Project Online resource

Spice

Project Online resource

MOOC and school label

SENSE-STEAM wiki and “The Learning Companion”

Online resource

A guide with real-life examples from education, research, and business.

OCED STIP COMPASS

STREAM IT project National inspiration hubs

SciCultureD

Project Planning tool University

It is a free, transdisciplinary planning tool designed to help create courses, modules, or activities addressing societal challenges. It combines design thinking with creative teaching methods, using interactive tools to plan playfully. Outcomes can range from public performances to products or interventions.

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

it can support the STEM Panel, and expand it to include STEAM practices (3.2 pg. 8, “In 2025, set up a European STEM Executive Panel at top business/political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the European Skills High Level Board and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party”.)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 2 D3.3 SEER D7.2

Evidence: SENSE Policy Brief VI SEER D7.2 Teaching, Learning and Assessing Creative and Critical Thinking Skills

Development and testing of a EU transdisciplinary STEAM-focused curriculum at secondary, vocational and university education level in lighthouse institutions

Co-design and deployment of a variety of options for a European holistic education curriculum focused on STEAM to be tested in longitudinal large scale control trials to derive evidence to inform policy decisions (Banerjee & Duflo, 2009) for step-by-step progressive pathways, taking into account the STEAM criteria (Collaboration, Disciplinary inter-relationships, Thinking-making-doing, Creativity, Real-world connection, Inclusion / Personalisation / Empowerment and equity) and EU priorities (focus on skills-based education, digital skills, industry relations, etc.). To inform policies on intersectionality, studies should investigate the effectiveness of STEAM programs and holistic curriculum by variables of vulnerability (gender, country, disability, special learning needs, family background, family support, etc.), and teachers/lecturer ability of diverse curricula and teaching approaches, including a holistic curriculum based on challenges (such as climate change and health instead of subjects)

Examples

Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

H-Farm Curriculum Primary School Middle High School

A secondary education teaching program based on the holistic International Bacchaurate curriculum expanded to include STEM in collaboration with the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), integrates science, research, and innovation, fostering interdisciplinary learning and technological advancements in education and cultural heritage.

IB Silicon Valley

Curriculum Middle

The holistic International Bacchaurate curriculum Middle Years Programme (MYP) is enhanced with arts curriculum to encourages students to engage in both visual and performing arts, fostering interdisciplinary connections between artistic expression and STEM subjects. Through inquiry-based learning, students develop skills in creativity, communication, and innovation, essential for STEAM education.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon, Pillar 2 and WIDERA

More examples: [International Bacchalaureate transdisciplinary program](#) [IB in Public Schools](#) [IB in Greece](#) [Still I rise STEAM INC](#) [India development of national curricula](#)

Suggested time frame: After action “Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum and school”; FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the scope providing indications for conducting extensive research on the assessment of actions to inform policy making (3.2 pg. 8, In 2025, set up a European STEM Executive Panel at top business/political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the European Skills High Level Board and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party.)

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 1, D3.3](#) [SENSE recommendation 1](#)

Evidence: [Road-STEAMer D2.3](#) [SENSE D4.4](#) [SEER D3.2](#) [JRC et al 2024](#) [Banerjee & Duflo, 2009](#) [Road-STEAMer-D4.1](#) [Road-STEAMer-D2.2](#)
[Durall, Carter & Burns 2022](#)

Investigate the efficacy of policies to increase hybrid and blended learning to make STEAM educational more accessible

Research should investigate how hybrid and blended learning formats can address barriers, which can be physical or digital, to make STEAM curriculum, educational resources, tools, and facilities equally available to all students. Research should investigate the impact of policies to increase hybrid and blended (online and physical learning - beyond current only online or only physical learning) STEAM curriculum offers, and their efficacy in increasing accessibility to students, in particular from learners with difficulty to physically access secondary and tertiary education or language barriers.

Examples

Blended learning high school

Program Middle High School

Dwight Schools offer a Blended Learning Program, combining traditional classroom education with online learning through Dwight Global Online School. This allows students worldwide to pursue rigorous academics and personal passions simultaneously, with flexible course options.

Revere High School (USA)

Online resource High School

successfully transformed a low-performing school to winning several awards, through a blended learning approach, setting it as a national (US) example of the type of programmatic systems change needed to move our schools forward, through flipped learning, iPads, SMARTBoard and monitoring progresses with iWalkthrough

UDL-BOE Blended learning in schools

Project (Funded)

Interactive tool Middle High School

a project funded by Erasmus+ it focuses on developing practical tools to help teachers deliver effective and engaging learning in a digital space, addressing two key areas: inclusion and digital pedagogical competences, with the main target group being second-level teachers. The approach will be based on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework (Cast.org), an inclusive approach to teaching and learning that offers all students an equal opportunity to fulfil their potential. This framework offers students different options for accessing, building and internalising learning.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

More examples: [\[SPICE academy\]](#) [SORA online middle school and highschool](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the "Pilot STEM education centers ecosystem" by suggesting the use of blended and hybrid learning, increasing accessibility for learners both physically and virtually. (3.2 pg. 9, "Pilot STEM education centres for school education, including VET schools, across the EU with the goal of improving how STEM is delivered and experienced in primary and secondary education")

Related policy recommendations: Four key social dimensions: co-creation, access, agency, and most importantly identity (SENSE) National government should ensure that inclusion in education acknowledges the intersecting challenges faced by students who belong to multiple underrepresented groups. This includes addressing language and cultural barriers to make STEAM education more accessible and relevant to diverse populations (RoadSTEAMer)

Evidence: [Allan, 2019](#) [Ahuja et al. 2023](#) [European Education Area report: how blended learning can make education more inclusive](#) [EU Blended mobility implementation guide for Erasmus+ higher education mobility KA131 guidance](#) [Dziuban et al. 2018](#) [SEER D3.1](#)

Effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning paradigms to support learning preferences and needs of diverse learners to increase inclusivity and improve skills

Longitudinal study to systematically test a variety of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning options to support diverse learning preferences and diverse assessment (skills-based), integrating the EU Digital Compass and Life Comp. To support the EU and Member States in defining and adopting a unified STEAM education strategy, research should be conducted to on the effectiveness of educational paradigms and available learning options to replace or heavily revise traditional national education paradigms. Interdisciplinary skills-based (rather than knowledge-based) educations, focused on real world challenges, can provide several economic benefits to European nations, off-setting the cost of a systemic change to the EU educational system. Research should test (i.e., with experimental trials) multiple STEAM and transdisciplinary (existing or new) learning approaches and evaluate which approach is most effective for which type of learner, including learners with disabilities or belonging to vulnerable groups (incl. intersectionality); such program include Universal Design for Learning (to be applied to STEAM education), the International Baccaalureate with STEM (in particular the Career-related Program), the Finnish STEM education program, etc.

Examples

H-Farm

Centre Program Primary-High school University

A secondary education teaching program based on the holistic International Bacchlaurate curriculum expanded to include STEM in collaboration with the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), integrates science, research, and innovation, fostering interdisciplinary learning and technological advancements in education and cultural heritage. The International Bacchalaurate has proven more successful than national curricula in improving students skills (Dulun& Lane, 2023)

School of Humanity (online middle and high school)

Centre Middle High school

Developed int he US with learning hubs worldwide, it partners with schools and with industries. It received several awards and it is based on a balance of interactive online learning, with time for offline, parent-led activities Instead of subjects, learners have daily workshops.

UDL-BOE Blended learning in schools

Project (Funded)

Interactive tool Middle High school

A project funded by Erasmus+ it focuses on developing practical tools to help teachers deliver effective and engaging learning in a digital space, addressing two key areas: inclusion and digital pedagogical competences, with the main target group being second-level teachers. The approach will be based on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework (Cast.org), an inclusive approach to teaching and learning that offers all students an equal opportunity to fulfil their potential. This framework offers students different options for accessing, building and internalising learning.

More examples: IN-STEAM

[International Bacchalaureate transdisciplinary program.](#)

[IB in public schools](#)

IB in Greece

[SpicE academy.](#)

Still I rise

Teacher Academy course "Universal Design for Learning: Strategies and Digital Tools to Support All Learners" and "Multi-Tiered Support System (MTSS) and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) for Academic and Behavioral Growth"

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 destination "Innovative Research on Social and Economic Transformations" and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to broaden its impact on under-represented and marginalized groups and increase employability.

Related policy recommendations: SEER D7.2 Road-STEAMer recommendation 7 D3.3

Evidence: Dulun& Lane, 2023 Thoma, Farassopoulos & Lousta, 2023 Road-STEAMer D4.2 Quigley et al., 2019

STEAM roadmap for Science Education in Horizon Europe

Funding Instruments: Horizon Europe and Erasmus (2026-27), FP10 (2028-2034)

[coordinating with: European STEM Executive Panel | Union of Skills | Council for societal challenges and EU national policies]

Mission education: systemic change of the educational system and assessment: skills-focused, transdisciplinary, inclusive, AI-enabled

Relevant for:

- Research (DG RTD)
- Education (DG EAC)
- Employment (DG EMPL)
- ICT and digital (DG CNECT)
- STEM strategic plan
- Expands the STEM strategic plan

What is STEAM?

Actions categorisation

<https://www.road-steamer.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058405

Research actions

Priority area 1	1A Redefine STEAM as a Holistic Curriculum across Europe
Strengthening the STEAM Curriculum at National and EU level	1B Develop STEAM Learning Materials, Teacher Resources and incentives
	2A Prioritize STEAM Training for Educators and school/university leaders
Priority area 2	2B Foster inclusive and supportive Learning Environments harnessing AI and digital tools
Enhancing Teacher Training and the Learning Environment	3A Develop STEAM career design and integrated learning pathways
	3B Support agile partnerships with organizations to address industry and societal needs
Priority area 3	4A Establish flexible, Inclusive and supportive STEAM education
Aligning STEAM education and career design with societal and industrial needs - STEAM literate citizens	3B Support agile partnerships with organizations to address industry and societal needs
	4A Establish flexible, Inclusive and supportive STEAM education
Priority area 4	4A Establish flexible, Inclusive and supportive STEAM education
Promoting equity with transdisciplinary, effective inclusive STEAM education paradigms	4A Establish flexible, Inclusive and supportive STEAM education
	4B Promote Intersectional approaches in STEAM, improving accessibility

Past | STEM edu strategic plan |

	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EU Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum / school / university and assessment									
Investigation of what the arts, design and creativity bring to STEAM education and derive best practices									
STEM competence framework 2026									
Systematic organization and testing of STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment									
Deployment and investigation of education and training through citizen science applied to STEAM									
Development and testing of a STEAM transdisciplinary curriculum and assessment at secondary, vocational and university education level in lighthouse institutions									
200.000 STEM students and staff trained in innovation and entrepreneurship by 2028									
Research on STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment to investigate and test best practices									
STEM Entrepreneurship education									
Training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM									
Integrate STEAM education in Horizon Europe Pillar 2 calls									
EU University alliance on STEAM									
Research on STEAM (lack of) career selection									
Development of networks, centres and alliances (incl. equipment) of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for mutual learning on STEAM									
Deployment and investigation of new approach to teachers' training (pre-service and in-service) for transdisciplinary education									
STEM career design									
STEM career exploration centers									
STEM skills founderies 2026									
Schools/university collaborations with local actors									
Capacity building in public administrations for multi-stakeholder collaborations (open-schooling)									
Joint diplomas, degrees, microcredentials with industry/civic organizations - fast tracking creditization at EU level									
An economic case for inclusive STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education									
Learning Environment design and its impact on learning outcomes									
Effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning paradigms to support learning preferences and needs of diverse learners to increase inclusivity and improve skills									
STEM Futures: in 2026 successful practices for girls and women									
Mentorship programs and scholarships for underrepresented groups									
Investigate the efficacy of policies to increase hybrid and blended learning to make STEAM educational more accessible									
By 2030 share of students enrolled in STEM in VET 45% (1 of 4 female)									
By 2030 share of students enrolled in ICT PhD 5% (1 of 3 female)									
1 million girls in STEM by 2028									
By 2030 share of students enrolled in STEM in tertiary 32% (2 of 5 female)									

Past | STEM edu strategic plan |

2034 Roadmap future digital education and skills | HE 2026 | 2027 | FP10 2028 | 2029 | 2030 | 2031 | 2032 | 2033

Union of Skills

EU teachers and trainers agenda | AI in education initiatives | Increasing accessibility of higher education

Investigation of what the arts, design and creativity bring to STEAM education and derive best practices

Triangulate literature with bottom-up evidence of which contribution and under which conditions the arts and design bring effective benefits to STEAM education, including mental health and career readiness, in order and derive best practices of interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary education along the educational continuum (primary school to lifelong learning) within the European context. Investigate how strengthening the arts element in STEAM is helpful in trauma-conscious education, in which art can serve as a healing tool for traumatized or struggling students and to help teachers of STEM subjects to recognize art's relevance.

Examples

Cultural Learning Alliance Project

Project Primary Middle School

Is an activity, where Eastbourne's STEAM project used art and science to explore plastic pollution through photography, sculpture, journaling, graphic design, and culminating in a public exhibition

More examples: Arts at CERN CREAM digital art project Particle Physics and the visual arts EASE Quantum Visions Vertigo S+T+Arts

Creation features

Program Primary Middle School

This is a STEAM-based **program**, an experiential learning approach that fosters curiosity, resilience, and leadership, ensuring students build knowledge progressively and develop essential life skills

Potential funding instrument

Horizon, Pillar 2 and WIDERA

Suggested time frame 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action supports and expands the plan advocating a stronger focus on the STEAM approach that supports holistic learning, curriculum design, that can be applied to create "Joint transnational programmes and short courses" in more informed STEAM approach. (3.2, pg. 10 "Develop joint transnational programmes and short courses leading to microcredentials in strategic STEM sectors, as identified in the Competitiveness Compass, through the Centres of Vocational Excellence and European Universities alliances. In close cooperation with their respective innovation ecosystems and with EU skills academies: i) boost the available range of joint programmes and microcredentials in STEM, including with a STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) educational approach

Related policy recommendations: RoadSTEAMer Recommendation 1 (D3.3)

Evidence: SENSE D3.2 (4.1 pg. 29) Road-STEAMer D3.1 Road-STEAMer D2.2 Penprase, B.E. (2018) Pirrie, A. (2019) Road-STEAMer-D2.2 Road-STEAMer-D4.1 STEM Competencies, Challenges, and Measurements, Biagi F.

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

EU Council of societal challenges to introduce a challenge on education

EU Council of societal challenges is advised to introduce a challenge on education and/or embed transversally education in all challenges, i.e., transdisciplinary STEAM approaches to support the climate emergency and STEAM focus on arts and skills-based open schooling approach to support mental health.

We advocate for the stronger integration of education—school education, teacher training, and tertiary education—into the European research and innovation (R&I) agenda, in response to the Expert Group's Align, Act, Accelerate Recommendation 7. This is an opportunity to enhance the existing collaborative framework between universities, research institutions, governments, civil society, and industry by explicitly recognising education as a driver of innovation, resilience, and societal transformation. Emphasising methodologies such as Open Schooling, STEAM education, Living Labs, Co-design, and Informal and Non-formal Learning, we call for dedicated funding, governance inclusion, support for transdisciplinary ecosystems, and investment in teacher capacity. Education is positioned not merely as preparatory but as an active co-creator of knowledge-based, human-centred solutions to complex societal challenges, contributing to a more inclusive, sustainable, and secure European future.

Examples

Schools as Living Labs

Project

Primary

Middle

High School

Living Labs are open-innovation spaces where students, schools, citizens, and organizations co-create STEAM-based solutions to real-world problems. The SALL project tested this approach in 400+ schools, showing strong results: 77% of teachers reported improved student independence and problem-solving, while 78% noted enhanced professional development in project-based learning and open schooling.

Make it Open

Project

Framework

Primary

Middle School

Empowering schools to act as drivers of community well-being by building synergies between educational institutions, enterprises, and civil society organisations. The project facilitated the co-design and implementation of activities in which students addressed real-life local challenges in partnership with their communities. Drawing on tools and methodologies from the maker movement, the initiative promoted hands-on, inquiry-based learning while strengthening schools' roles as hubs of social innovation and local engagement.

Potential funding instrument

EU council of societal challenges

Suggested time frame: FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025 This action expands the plan

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 5 D3.3

Evidence: SENSE D4.3

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

C. Attract more students from diverse backgrounds to STEM studies in secondary education, VET and tertiary education by launching:

- i. the STEM Tech Talent Induction. Induction activities designed to attract young people to STEM careers and involving role models and entrepreneurs will be implemented by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT).*

Research on STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment to investigate and test best practices

Building on the action “systematic organization of open-access STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment, identification of gaps and development in all EU languages with feedback loops for improvement”, systematic data collection on the use of STEAM teaching material and practices to derive the most effective practices in diverse contexts and for diverse learners’ profiles. Specific research should be conducted on teachers/lecturer ability and compliance and encountered challenges for large scale implementation of the STEAM approach in government educational institutions.

Examples

STEAMonEdu MOOC

Project

Framework

The project aims to boost STE(A)M education by supporting educators' professional development through blended training and an online community. It will create a STE(A)M education framework, including curricula, competencies, and policies. The project also offers a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) for educators, guides on best practices, and tools for STE(A)M policy influencers, focusing on diversity and competence development.

More examples: [SpicE MOOC](#) [Circular STEM](#)

STEAM Hub Leadership Programme (UK)

Program

Primary

Middle

High School

The STEAM Hub Leadership Programme empowers teachers to design STEAM curricula and build industry partnerships while equipping diverse young people with skills for STEAM careers. It fosters an inclusive STEAM community in Camden, influencing policy and regional growth.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2

Suggested time frame: FP10

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It can expand the European STEM Executive Panel to include the STEAM approach (3.2 pg. 8 encourage the centres and alliances to coordinate their STEM offer and to pool and share their investments in STEM infrastructure, equipment, and educational technologies.)

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 2](#)

Evidence: [SEER, Focus group 7](#) [Road-STEAMer D2.3](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Propose new **2030 EU-level STEM targets**. By 2030:

- i) *the share of students enrolled in STEM fields in initial medium-level VET should be at least 45%²⁰; at least 1 out of every 4 students should be female.²¹*
- ii) *the share of students enrolled in STEM fields at tertiary level should be at least 32%²², with at least 2 out of every 5 students female.*
- iii) *the share of students enrolled in ICT PhD programmes should be at least 5%²³, with at least 1 out of every 3 students female.*

Development of networks, centres and alliances (incl. equipment) of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for mutual learning on STEAM

Development of networks of teachers/lecturers/head teachers/principals for hybrid (face-to-face and online training) mutual learning on STEAM curriculum and STEAM schools/universities., through both physical and digital collaborative environments, for example through twinning programs, teachers exchanges, MOOCs and face-to-face events for peer-to-peer learning, to promote knowledge exchange and the dissemination of successful STEAM practices.

Examples

Scientix

Online resource

Formal

It is the STEM Education Community in Europe. It offers the space for all people working in the field of science education to exchange, collaborate and learn from each other. It includes the STEM Alliance, a platform for STEM educators and companies

EASE – EuropeAn Network of STEAM Educators

Online resource

Primary

Middle

a non-profit organization that aims at enhancing the work of all educators and teachers in terms of promoting STEAM skills with children, young people and adults in formal and non-formal education.

PHERECLOS project

Project (Funded)

Primary

Middle

High School

A Horizon project, building upon the experience of Children's Universities (CUs) in Europe and beyond. Due to their engagement with children and young people, they help to break down institutional boundaries between universities and the wider society, focusing on open schooling. STEAM education is highlighted. The project developed a complete teacher training toolkit. There is also a collection of good practices.

More examples:

STEAMonEdu MOOC

School As living Labs (SALL EU project)

[ArtsWork creating seven STEAM networks in SE England]

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It expands by including a STEAM focus on the creation of centres and alliances, that could be focused on specific sub-sectors of STEM (3.2 pg. 10 D ii. encourage the centres and alliances to coordinate their STEM offer and to pool and share their investments in STEM infrastructure, equipment and educational technologies.)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 4, D3.3

Evidence: SEER D3.2

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM

Development and testing of training for school heads, school leaders, university deans and policy makers on STEAM and related actions such as the effect of a "STEAM coordinator" or STEAM specialist in each school or university

Examples

Innovative Leaders Institute

Program

Formal

The Innovative Leaders Institute is a year-long program designed for school leaders aiming to transform current practices and bring high-quality STEM education to their students.

Purdue Polytechnic Institute

Program

University

Master of Science in Technology Leadership and Innovation with a focus on STEM Education Leadership. Graduates of the STEM Education Leadership program are prepared to become leaders in integrated STEM in a variety of positions including university professors, K-12 teachers, policymakers, administrators, informal learning specialists, and others. Participants learn to conduct research that informs practice.

McDaniel College STEM Instructional Leader

Program

University

This graduate certificate program aimed at preparing educators to take on STEM leadership roles within their schools and districts. The program is delivered online, consisting of 18 credits, and focuses on equipping participants with the skills necessary to make a significant impact in STEM education.

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

More examples: [Navigate EdTech – Choosing Wisely for Learners](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

this action expands the plan Alignment with the JRC Science for Policy Brief "STEM and STEAM education, and disciplinary integration: a guide to informed policy action": "Whole school approaches "imply collective and collaborative action in and by a school community to improve student learning, behaviour and well-being, and the conditions that support these"[27] by engaging the local community, school leaders, middle management, teaching and non-teaching staff, learners, parents, and families." (pg. 5)

Related policy recommendations: to be developed

Evidence: [Douthit, 2021](#); [Abbas et al. 2024](#); [SEER 2.3 \(2.3 pg. 15\)](#) [SEER focus group 7 \(pg. 6\)](#) [SEER D7.2 \(pg. 14\)](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

ii. Support the development of joint education programmes (Bachelors, Masters, and Doctoral levels) and specialist training for strategic STEM sectors, leveraging the skills academies and the European Universities Alliances. This includes joint degrees and future European degrees in digital technologies (e.g., AI, quantum, cybersecurity) and interdisciplinary degrees applying these technologies to sectors like health and biotech, as well as training for Destination Earth²⁴ technologies (e.g., climate modelling, circular engineering).

D. Address employers' needs in VET and tertiary education by means of the following actions:

- i. *Develop joint transnational programmes and short courses leading to micro-credentials in strategic STEM sectors, as identified in the Competitiveness Compass, through the Centres of Vocational Excellence and European Universities alliances. In close cooperation with their respective innovation ecosystems and with EU skills academies: i) boost the available range of joint programmes and micro-credentials in STEM, including with a STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) educational approach, ii) encourage the centres and alliances to coordinate their STEM offer and to pool and share their investments in STEM infrastructure, equipment and educational technologies; iii) encourage the centres and alliances to leverage private investment for the development of micro-credentials tailored to upskilling and reskilling the European workforce in strategic STEM sectors; iv) support and monitor the take-up by employers recruiting talent with micro-credentials issued with EU support.*

Propose new **2030 EU-level STEM targets**. By 2030:

- i) *the share of students enrolled in STEM fields in initial medium-level VET should be at least 45%²⁰; at least 1 out of every 4 students should be female.²¹*
- ii) *the share of students enrolled in STEM fields at tertiary level should be at least 32%²², with at least 2 out of every 5 students female.*
- iii) *the share of students enrolled in ICT PhD programmes should be at least 5%²³, with at least 1 out of every 3 students female.*

Example categorization

Type of Education:

- Curriculum/Program
- Project (funded)
- Initiative
- Online Resource
- Course/Activity
- Teachers/lecturer training
- Interactive tool/toolkit
- Model/Framework

Level of Education:

- Primary school
- Middle school
- High School
- University/tertiary
- Phd
- formal/non-formal
- Centre/Institute

C. Showcase and exchange good practices and foster mutual learning on attracting and supporting girls and women in STEM apprenticeships.

*Engaging with companies, research institutions, research and technology organisations and other stakeholders as part of the **European Alliance for Apprenticeships**, with a focus on increasing the proportion of female apprentices.*

Deployment and investigation of education and training through citizen science applied to STEAM

Identification of citizen science projects applied to STEAM, design and deployment of open science and citizen science projects for STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education, to investigate the effectiveness of citizen science as a learning practice, as well as providing data to current research (i.e., aligned with societal grand challenges).

Examples

Malta Science in the City

Activity Non-formal

Malta Science in the City is an Activity based on an annual festival that blends science, art, and innovation, encouraging public engagement through interactive exhibits, performances, and workshops emphasizing on Citizen Science, inviting the public to actively participate in scientific research and contribute to data collection. The event is part of the European Researchers' Night, helping bridge the gap between science and society.

National Geographic Citizen Science projects

Project Non-formal

Citizen science projects where volunteers help collect data for scientific research. These projects span various fields, including ecology and space, allowing individuals to contribute to real-world scientific discoveries. Participants can engage in activities like wildlife monitoring, weather observation, and environmental tracking.

[SENSE project report on the Citizen Science and Art-Practices Workshop - Deliverable 3.2](#)

Other projects [\[MOST \(Meaningful Open Schooling Connects Schools To Communities\) \]](#)

Potential funding instrument

Pillar 2 Cluster 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

[Coming soon]

Related policy recommendations: [SENSE recommendation 2, Policy-Brief-RP1-V1](#)

Evidence: [Road-STEAMer D3.1](#) [Vohland et al. 2021](#) [SENSE D3.4](#) [Sauermann, H. et al. \(2020\)](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

“Mission Education” - Systemic change of the educational system and assessment by orchestrating STEM/STEAM education research actions of EU funded projects for enhancing EU competitiveness through monitoring and scaling of actions for skills development, harnessing AI and digital technologies through a transdisciplinary inclusive approach to learning

Develop a Mission for the systemic innovation of EU education with the aim to orchestrate long-term systemic innovation for transdisciplinary inclusive technical education in the EU, though testing an EU curriculum and standardized testing, to inform and work in close coordination with the upcoming “European STEM executive Panel” and the European skills high level board (STEM Education Strategic Plan pg. 8) and European Skills Intelligence Observatory, to support the development of the STEM Education Strategic Plan’s goal of “Improve overall STEM skills intelligence based on international indicators and benchmarks, by measuring graduate outcomes in VET and tertiary education” (pg.8). Such program could overcome the “fragmentation of resources across programs” (pg. 12). It would coordinate EU funded research projects, collecting and analyzing qualitative and quantitative longitudinal data at every level (student, teacher, school, region, countries) to complement PISA assessment with more granular data, for the deployment and testing of digital education and AI in all educational levels, to scale existing successful projects and boost the opportunities that it provides for flexible (hybrid, blended, online) and inclusive (customized) skills-based STEAM education opportunities for vulnerable groups and learners with diverse abilities. It can be structured as the EU Missions (Cities, Adaptation, Soil, Ocean and Cancer), mobilizing systemic change through long-term (7-10 years) coordination of actions within and between European countries (as the National platforms in the Mission “Cities” and the “deep dives” of the Mission “Adaptation”) to deploy and investigate a step-by-step progressive pathway toward project-based, transdisciplinary, AI-enhanced transdisciplinary (challenge-based or phenomenon-based) education in line with EU priorities. The Mission Education should coordinate the definition of mixed methods, process and outcome indicators and sensemaking processes, collecting data and monitoring step-by-step progressive pathways of STEM and STEAM practices (beyond disciplinary silos), programs, schools and universities in the EU - assessing beyond knowledge also life skills and mental health/wellbeing- to inform policy making for evidence-based educational reforms.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and inclusive society; destination: “Innovative Research on Societal and Economic Transformation”) and cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and space); Erasmus

Examples: [EU Missions](#) [Mission Cities](#) [Mission Adaptation](#) [Impact pathways in the Mission Cities](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 + FP10 2028-34 (longitudinal action 7 to 10 years)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the STEM Strategic Plan to propose the creation of a long-term research action to orchestrate systemic innovation in EU education, supporting the Union of Skills, to support the EU in achieving the goal of Improve overall STEM skills intelligence based on international indicators and benchmarks (pg.8).

*Improve overall **STEM skills intelligence** based on international indicators and benchmarks, by measuring graduate outcomes in VET and tertiary education through the Eurograduate survey, and by better anticipating sector-specific skills needs as part of the future European Skills Intelligence Observatory and by leveraging the common European Data Space for Skills.*

Evidence: [Mazzuccato 2018](#) [Mazzuccato 2021](#) [Pokropek, 2025](#)

STEAM (lack of) career selection

Investigate the motivation of students exposed and not exposed to STEAM education and open schooling approaches integrating social and corporate collaborations, in selecting a STE(A)M education (secondary/vocational/tertiary) and a career in STE(A)M: identify barriers, enablers and biases.

Examples

Education and Training Monitor 2024 (Finland)

Online resource

Finland education focus on STEM does not increase STEM uptake.

CAREER project

Online resource Project (Funded) Non formal

funded by an ERC Starting Grant from the European Research Council (ERC). From School to Career: Towards A Career Perspective on the Labor Market Returns to Education (CAREER) is a five-year research project (2021-2026), funded by the European Research Council. It aims to develop a better understanding of workers' employment trajectories in the context of changing labour markets.

Pew Research Center survey

Online resource Non formal

Pew Research Center survey on why more American students do not pursue STEM majors

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, Cluster 2 destination 3

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action partly aligns with the STEM strategy plans where it expands the scope of proposed action of identifying the underlying the pre-existing causes and motivation of students on how to attract them to STEM education through STEAM approaches (3.2 pg. 8, "better anticipating sector-specific skills needs as part of the future European Skills Intelligence Observatory and by leveraging the common European Data Space for Skills.)

Evidence: Holmegaard, et al. 2014 Mandalapu & Gnog, 2019 Wang, Ye & Degol, 2017 Tandrayen-Ragoobur & Gokulsing, 2022

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

*In 2025, set up a **European STEM Executive Panel** at top business/ political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the **European Skills High Level Board** and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party.*

STEAM career design

Longitudinal study to design and test support for STEAM career design and exploration across the learner's journey (cradle to grave) aligned with EU priorities (Green Deal, competitiveness, security, democracy) and job market needs. Define and test a replicable methodology for career exploration and life design with a focus on STEAM.

Examples

Designing Your Life

Program University PhD

Through this program, students are able to identify their ideal life and career, in collaboration with executive coaches and academic advisors to design an individualized, goal-driven pathway.

STEAMULE

Interactive tool Project (Funded) Formal

The STEAMULE project challenges career-related prejudices, such as gender stereotypes, to inspire young people to explore diverse career options. It encourages informed reflection on career choices through discussions. Additionally, the project supports educational teams by providing training in teaching practices and new skills, aligned with the Pact for Teaching Excellence and polytechnic education goals.

STEAMiE

Interactive tool Primary Middle High school Formal

An educational game engine developed by Ohio University to expose middle school students to science career fields.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 + FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan.

Evidence: Road-STEAMer D7.4

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Funding for EDTECH startups to promote STEAM

fund EU start-ups to promote STEAM education, modular learning materials with online training for educators, harnessing AI for students customized online learning, potentially online educational activities with students across EU Member states.

Examples

AI learning apps for educators

Online resource University

Brian AI teaching assistant is a gamified learning app for all educators established in Switzerland and utilized by the University of St. Gallen

More example:

Khan Academy

Edtech programs

Program Middle School

Girls code it better is a 45h free program for girls at school, one afternoon a week at schools

Arduino

Online resource Middle High School

University

Used by over 50,000 schools and universities, Arduino Education offers open-source STEAM tools for learning electronics, programming, IoT, and robotics from middle school to university. It's taught at top institutions like MIT and widely used in high school STEM programs, especially in robotics clubs and science fairs. In Italy, it's integrated into national curricula for technology and engineering.

Potential funding instrument

Pillar 3 (i.e., EIT digital transformation)

Suggested time frame: FP10

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

It does not align with the STEM strategic plan.

Related policy recommendations: [Coming soon]

Evidence: [Coming soon]

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

An economic case for *inclusive* STEAM education in secondary and tertiary education

Calculate the economic case of increasing STEAM education at secondary and tertiary level to provide evidence for policy making, and specifically the economic case for developing learning paths and environment that are inclusive for underrepresented groups, including women and all genders, people with disabilities, autism, ADHD, sensory sensitivity, low socio-economic status, migration background, etc., in partnership with industry players and other organizations. A longitudinal study (control trial) can inform future policies on the economic advantages of developing tailored skills development and career support for STEAM experts that are otherwise unemployed or underemployed because of vulnerabilities.

Examples

Learning programs suitable for twice-exceptional students

Centre

Formal

Bridges Academy is a leading school for gifted and twice-exceptional students (2e). Our students have an individual mix of high abilities and learning challenges.

LiNC-IT

Program

Formal

employment program that collaborates with government, nonprofits, and employers to provide employment opportunities for individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder

Companies and programs with inclusive culture and programs

Auticon

Microsoft's Neurodiversity Hiring Program

SAP's Autism at Work

IBM's Neurodiversity Advancement Initiative

Google Autism Career Program in collaboration with the Stanford Neurodiversity Project

Specialisterne

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 destination "Innovative Research on Social and Economic Transformations"

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the plan to broaden its impact on under-represented and marginalized group and increase employability.

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: SEER D3.1 Perales & Aróstegui, 2024 OECD Learning Compass for Mathematics

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Learning Environment design and its impact on learning outcomes

Research on the physical environment impact on educational outcomes for a variety of students' needs and abilities (including disabilities) to design STEAM spaces that consider the overall quality of the learning experience alongside functionality, and promoting participatory, reflective design strategies that create spaces reflecting the views and feelings of all participants. The traditional classroom is a “symbol” for a particular educational approach; a STEAM space is essentially a “not-a-classroom” space (SENSE) that can include labs, outdoor learning and learning through experiences with the school/university community. Investigate diverse pathways into science education through inclusive spaces, by creating platforms and opportunities for students and the school community to contribute to the design of learning environments. Research to provide evidence-based design of inclusive learning environments that are suitable for learners and lecturers with high sensory sensitivity or other needs (moving, privacy, rest, sensory rooms, labs) and its relation to making spaces accessible to everyone (SENSE), supporting wellbeing for all, through a positive impact on mental health, which should then be included into teachers training (pre-service and on-service).

Examples

Labs

Centre Middle High School

UCL Academy is a specialist school emphasizing a STEAM-focused curriculum. The school offers specialized facilities, including science laboratories, engineering suites, and performance spaces, to support its interdisciplinary approach to education

More examples: [SPICE academy](#) [STEAM.SENSE lab Odyssea](#)

OTTER

Project (Funded)

Primary-High School Formal

an Erasmus+ project on learning outside the classroom, specifically to improve scientific knowledge, get closer to STEAM subjects. It provides toolkits and guidelines practitioners can use to teach outside the classroom.

SENSE project Deliverables

[D5.1 Scoping report on STEAM spaces](#)

[D5.2. Report on Evaluation of space strategies for the STEAM Roadmap](#)

[D5.3 Self-experimentation toolkits and design principles for STEAM spaces](#)

[D5.4 Policy recommendations: STEAM spaces and the New European Bauhaus](#)

Sensory and Quiet rooms

Education institutions have sensory rooms or quiet rooms to be used for meltdown prevention

Universal Design

Design for All

Outdoor learning

Examples:
[The Green School in Bali](#)

[UBC MOOC on STEM Outside](#)

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to promote more inclusive learning to increase the uptake of STEM education.

Related policy recommendations: [SENSE recommendation 1](#), [D5.4](#)

Evidence: [SENSE D5.1](#) [SENSE D5.4](#) [Aron, 2002](#) [McAllister, 2010](#) [Byers, Terry, Wesley Imms, and Elizabeth Hartnell-Young. 2014](#)
[Pluess, 2019](#) [Butera, et al., 2020](#) [Rose, 2000](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Increase STEAM teaching prestige through fostering schools/university collaborations with local actors

Increase STEAM teaching prestige through fostering structured schools/university collaborations with local actors (industry players, SMEs, civic organizations, governmental institutions) to equip educators with practical knowledge that they can transfer into the classroom and increase the school/university reputation. Develop best practices and investigate the impact of collaborations on teachers/lecturers perceived self-efficacy and reputation.

Examples

School As living Labs (SALL EU project)

Project (Funded) Primary Secondary

Schools As Living Labs" (SALL) is a project that adapts open-schooling and Living Lab methodologies to create and test new tools for schools in 10 countries. It involves 412 school communities, aiming to support the design and implementation of living-lab activities, foster community-building, and promote sustainable open-schooling practices across Europe.

SATO

Program Primary Secondary

The Schools Across the Ocean program, developed by the University of Exeter, Emirates Literature Foundation, and Khorfakkan University, helps teachers address climate education. Involving 14 schools in the UK and UAE, it engages 400 children to explore ocean-related issues using a specially designed toolkit, fostering community connections and action.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe or Erasmus+

More examples: [\[SciCultureD\]](#) [\[EFPM839 Transdisciplinary Collaborations for Creative Futures\]](#) [Teach For All](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

Aligns with the European STEM Executive Panel development (3.2 pg. 8, "to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education"; "Supported by Erasmus+, these centres will create dynamic learning ecosystems that drive innovation in STEM teaching and learning in schools, by stepping up cooperation with businesses, science museums, STEM organisations, libraries, cultural associations, creative industries, universities and research institutions")

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 4, D3.3

Evidence: [SEER D2.2 \(3.2\)](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Multi-stakeholder collaborations through open-schooling

Multi-stakeholder collaborations through open-schooling, fuse the STEAM approach, open schooling environment and living lab practice within an empowering partnership based on local level collaboration between formal, non-formal and informal technology and science education providers, enterprises, local businesses, cultural institutions, and civil society (also called “STEAM Learning Ecologies”; ref. SENSE, SEER). Research should investigate how STEAM Learning Ecologies can sustain the implementation and cost of STEAM teaching and learning practices, and how it can foster a systemic change in the education system through multi-stakeholder collaborations. Schools and universities innovate their role – aligned with Europe vision of systemic change implemented in the EU Missions– which is enacted through a revised role of public institutions as enablers of systemic change by activating the local ecosystem, empowering trainers and learners to become themselves agents of change (SENSE). The investigation of the effectiveness of partnerships could include sharing or sponsoring spaces and equipment, as well as mentorship programmes to foster meaningful interaction between professionals, scientists, and students, ensuring that students gain insights into real-world applications of their learning. Partnerships should align educational outcomes with labour market needs and societal challenges, particularly in sectors requiring both technical and creative skills, such as digital innovation, design, and renewable energy, as well as considering top skills that can foster employment (i.e., Data Analysis and Interpretation; Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning; Cybersecurity; Cloud Computing; Programming and Software Development; Analytical/Mathematical Thinking; People Management and Leadership; Communication and Teamwork; Adaptability & Innovation; Technical Proficiency and IT Skills (SEER). Collaboration with industries and livinglabs can provide the necessary labs and materials for STEAM activities.

Examples

SALL

Project (Funded)

Toolkit

Primary

High School

Schools As Living Labs" (SALL) is a (project) that adapts open-schooling and Living Lab methodologies to create and test new tools for schools in 10 countries. It involves 412 school communities, aiming to support the design and implementation of living-lab activities, foster community-building, and promote sustainable open-schooling practices across Europe.

More examples: [\[Smithsonian Museum and Ukraine Ministry of Education and Science\]](#) [\[Polifactory: fablab of Politecnico di Milano\]](#)
[\[InChildHealth example of project\]](#) [Bosch-Stiftung Germany](#) [Politecnico di Milano: Festival dell'ingegneria](#)

OSOS

Model

Interactive tool

Primary

High School

The OSOS Open Schooling Model helps school leaders explore ways to transform schools into innovation hubs, enabling effective co-design and use of educational content, tools, and services for personalized science learning and teaching.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 all pillars and Missions, Cluster 3 EIT and EIE, and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action supports the plan expanding it to STEAM (3.2 pg. 8, In 2025, “The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education”)

Related policy recommendations: [SENSE recommendation 2 & 4 \(SENSE D5.4\)](#) [Collaboration between Education and Industry \(SEER D3.2\)](#)

Evidence: [SENSE D5.5](#) [SEER D3.2](#) [STREAM-IT \(forthcoming\)](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Mentorship programs and scholarships for underrepresented groups

Research the effectiveness of implementing targeted interventions for vulnerable and underrepresented students in STEAM, such as mentorship programs, peer to peer buddy programs, scholarships, access to a range of educational options and approaches (including part-time and micro-credentials) that can support a variety of their needs such as reduced mobility to diverse abilities, safety, religion or cost, sensory issues, anxiety, neurodiversity, and socio-economic status.

Examples

Schools and Universities support programs

Stepchange: mentally healthy universities framework of UniversitiesUK (whole university approach)

Framework University

Politecnico di Milano program for students with diverse abilities

Resources, mentorship, and networking

Primary - High School University Non formal Initiative

Latinas in STEM empowers Latina women in STEM fields by offering resources, mentorship, and networking opportunities to support their success in education and careers

Scholarships (from sponsors)

University Non formal Formal Initiative

Google's Women Techmakers offers scholarships programs to women in computer science and related fields, providing financial support, mentorship, and networking opportunities.

MESA Community support program for disadvantaged students

Mathematics, Engineering, Science Achievement (MESA) is an academic preparation program for pre-college, community college and university-level students. Established in 1970 in California, the program provides academic support to students from educationally disadvantaged backgrounds throughout the education pathway so they will excel in math and science and ultimately attain four-year degrees in science, technology, engineering or math (STEM) fields. MESA has been named among the top five most innovative public programs in the USA: an initiative of the Ford Foundation, the Kennedy School of Government at Harvard University, and the Council for Excellence in Government

Middle High School University Initiative

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action does not align with STEM strategy plan, but it can expand by including vulnerable and under-represented groups to their mentorship program along with scholarship that can improve the attractiveness to STEM careers and education.

Related policy recommendations: While gender diversity remains critical, future policies should adopt a more comprehensive approach to inclusion in STEAM education, addressing barriers faced by ethnic minorities, low-income students, and students with disabilities providing access to a range of educational options and approaches that can cater the variety of their needs, and provide funding to monitor the effectiveness of those measures. [Road-STEAMer recommendation 8 D3.3](#)

Evidence: Tandrayen-Ragoobur & Gokulsing, 2022 [The_SEER_FocusGroup05 SENSE D6.1](#) [SEER D3.2](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Investigate the efficacy of policies to increase hybrid and blended learning to make STEAM educational more accessible

Research should investigate how hybrid and blended learning formats can address barriers, which can be physical or digital, to make STEAM curriculum, educational resources, tools, and facilities equally available to all students. Research should investigate the impact of policies to increase hybrid and blended (online and physical learning - beyond current only online or only physical learning) STEAM curriculum offers, and their efficacy in increasing accessibility to students, in particular from learners with difficulty to physically access secondary and tertiary education or language barriers.

Examples

Blended learning high school

Program Middle High School

Dwight Schools offer a Blended Learning Program, combining traditional classroom education with online learning through Dwight Global Online School. This allows students worldwide to pursue rigorous academics and personal passions simultaneously, with flexible course options.

Revere High School (USA)

Online resource High School

successfully transformed a low-performing school to winning several awards, through a blended learning approach, setting it as a national (US) example of the type of programmatic systems change needed to move our schools forward, through flipped learning, iPads, SMARTBoard and monitoring progresses with iWalkthrough

UDL-BOE Blended learning in schools

Project (Funded)

Interactive tool Middle High School

a project funded by Erasmus+ it focuses on developing practical tools to help teachers deliver effective and engaging learning in a digital space, addressing two key areas: inclusion and digital pedagogical competences, with the main target group being second-level teachers. The approach will be based on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework (Cast.org), an inclusive approach to teaching and learning that offers all students an equal opportunity to fulfil their potential. This framework offers students different options for accessing, building and internalising learning.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

More examples: [SPICE academy](#) [SORA online middle school and highschool](#)

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the "Pilot STEM education centers ecosystem" by suggesting the use of blended and hybrid learning, increasing accessibility for learners both physically and virtually. (3.2 pg. 9, "Pilot STEM education centres for school education, including VET schools, across the EU with the goal of improving how STEM is delivered and experienced in primary and secondary education")

Related policy recommendations: Four key social dimensions: co-creation, access, agency, and most importantly identity (SENSE) National government should ensure that inclusion in education acknowledges the intersecting challenges faced by students who belong to multiple underrepresented groups. This includes addressing language and cultural barriers to make STEAM education more accessible and relevant to diverse populations (RoadSTEAMer)

Evidence: [Allan, 2019](#) [Ahuja et al. 2023](#) [European Education Area report: how blended learning can make education more inclusive](#) [EU Blended mobility implementation guide for Erasmus+ higher education mobility KAI31 guidance](#) [Dziuban et al. 2018](#) [SEER D3.1](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Deployment and investigation of new approach to teachers' training (pre-service and in-service) for transdisciplinary education (pre-service and in-service): STEM competence framework for educators and school leaders

Development and application of transdisciplinary, project-based, student-focused STEAM frameworks, such as the STEAMComp Edu, possibly aligned with the ESCO classification, for training educators in Europe, at all educational levels. Research is needed to investigate the effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary education frameworks in increasing teachers/lecturers, school heads, students and schools' proficiency in breaking silos when teaching STEAM subjects, fostering interdisciplinary, trainers' inclusive attitude and ability to collaborate among teachers, engage students and local actors. Include a multi-level governance component, addressing national training institutions (to be considered as multipliers) to adapt EU resources to specific contexts using tailored teachers training for collaborative project-based mindset, supported by content and tools.

Examples

STEAMComp Edu

Framework

Formal

Non-formal

It is a framework that focuses on developing the competencies needed to design and implement effective STEAM education. The framework primarily supports educators in creating inclusive, engaging, and innovative learning experiences for students.

More examples: [\[steamonedu\]](#) [LUMA Centre](#)

Still I rise educational approach

Formal

The humanitarian organization was nominated to the Nobel peace prize in 2023 for providing world-class education in vulnerable contexts. Teachers training include emotional intelligence, "critical and creative thinking, instilling deep passion and a concrete commitment to social justice and societal progress."

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

Aligns with the STEM competence framework which should be enlarged to STEAM holistic competence (3.2 pg. 9 "Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills.")

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 3 D3.3

Evidence: [SEER D2.2 \(3 pg. 27\)](#), [Spyropoulou & Kameas, 2023](#) [Oanh, 2025](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

A. Promote future-oriented STEM curricula in schools, VET and tertiary education by:

i. Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills.

EU Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum / school / university and assessment

From existing cases and scientific evidence of STEAM holistic curriculum and STEAM schools and universities, co-create with learners, lecturers and all stakeholders a pan-European definition and assessment that aligned with EU priorities (including digital education) and can be adaptable to national educational systems, identifying gaps and overlaps across EU MS and their alignment with EU priorities. This research action should also define indicators, collecting data and monitoring

Examples

Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

Framework

Penryn College, Cornwall UK

Curriculum

Middle School

STEAM **curriculum** embedded in an arts/science rich college in which the learner's journey is mapped through various stages ensuring character build and career build are developed simultaneously through each step

STEM School label

Strategy

A STEM School is defined as a school with a clear STEM strategy, characterised by different key elements and criteria. This definition is the result of the European STEM Schools Report which builds upon a vast literature review and a thorough consultation process with four groups of key stakeholders in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education. Those key stakeholders are schools, STEM teachers, Ministries of Education and STEM Industries. The report's criteria for "STEM Schools" identify key areas that can help schools advance and have a clearer strategy for STEM education (funded by the H2020 project Scientix 4 Grant agreement N. 101000063, coordinated by European Schoolnet EUN)

Nansledan School

Program

Primary School

This is a STEAM-based **program**, an experiential learning approach that fosters curiosity, resilience, and leadership, ensuring students build knowledge progressively and develop essential life skills

Centre for Research in Transdisciplinary Education

Research Center

This new Centre (est 2025) offers fertile dialogic ground to breed innovative ideas in educational research within and between subject disciplines. It draws on, and develops, new methodologies from arts-based, creative and post-qualitative methods through to exploratory quantitative approaches, working with STEAM and transdisciplinary educational practice and researching with community and industry partners

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe, Pillar 2, Cluster 2 "Culture, Creativity and inclusive society", destination "innovative research on social and economic transformation"

Suggested time frame 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns and enhances the plan for a pan-European STEM competence framework, including holistic curricula design for STEM skill competencies. This will also add an inclusive lens to assess STEM skills (3.2, pg. 9 "Developing by 2026 a STEM competence framework for all learners at all stages of education and a taxonomy of STEM skills within the ESCO classification. This will inspire and promote curriculum design, and assessment frameworks for STEM skills")

Related policy recommendations: RoadSTEAMer Recommendation 1 (D3.3) SEER D7.2

Evidence: Road-STEAMer-D2.3 Watts, D. S. and Richardson, J. W. (2020) SEER D7.2 Road-STEAMer-D2.2 Road-STEAMer-D4.1

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Systematic organization of open-access STEAM teaching material, practices and assessment, identification of gaps and development in all EU languages with feedback loops for improvement

STEAM material mapping, systematic organization, identification of gaps and development of open educational resources (including modules to be integrated into courses as well as holistic STEAM curricula) to be provided in a user-friendly platform, co-created with teachers and lecturers of diverse educational levels, organized by relevant variables (educational level, language, disciplines, time, inclusivity level, etc.). These materials should prioritise pedagogical relevance, ensuring they are meaningful rather than solely engaging or performative and based on real-life challenges and skills development (instead of knowledge-centred education), according for example to the EU “Lifecomp” and related to a range of careers exploration (in collaboration with external stakeholders including companies and governmental organizations). Starting by gathering already existing resources and making them accessible (in different languages) currently under-utilised resources from previous projects, including EU-funded initiatives, should be systematized in a one-stop-shop digital space where lecturers can easily find materials, share, find peer-to-peer support and provide feedback on pedagogical effectiveness and evidence from assessment that takes into account AI implications for learning and assessment.

Examples

Roadsteamer map of STEAM practices in Europe

Project Online resource

Scientix

Project Online resource

Spice MOOC and school label

Project Online resource

SENSE-STEAM wiki and “The Learning Companion”

Online resource

A guide with real-life examples from education, research, and business.

OCED STIP COMPASS

STREAM IT project National inspiration hubs

SciCultureD

Project Planning tool University

It is a free, transdisciplinary planning tool designed to help create courses, modules, or activities addressing societal challenges. It combines design thinking with creative teaching methods, using interactive tools to plan playfully. Outcomes can range from public performances to products or interventions.

Potential funding instrument

Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

it can support the STEM Panel, and expand it to include STEAM practices (3.2 pg. 8, “In 2025, set up a European STEM Executive Panel at top business/political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the European Skills High Level Board and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party”.)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 2 D3.3 SEER D7.2

Evidence: SENSE Policy Brief V1 SEER D7.2 Teaching, Learning and Assessing Creative and Critical Thinking Skills

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

STEAM career exploration centers

Experiment and test the co-creation of career exploration centers that students can attend from the last year of middle school to university, substituting a part of class hours, to promote authentic transdisciplinary learning, an informed understanding of career options and experiences, focused on careers in high demand and in relation to EU priorities (i.e, the Green Deal, cybersecurity, entrepreneurship, etc.). The centers can offer structured activities between secondary and tertiary education, or teachers/university lecturers training on career design support to students, which are investigated through longitudinal studies to co-design and test the effectiveness in particular for vulnerable students. The centers promote lifelong learning beyond the traditional school years and encourage inclusion of local actors, in collaboration with businesses that co-finance the centers.

Examples

Gereau Center for Applied Technology and Career Exploration

Centre Middle School

At the Gereau Center, career exploration is integrated into the eighth-grade (curriculum) through project-based learning, specialized courses, and hands-on experiences. Students explore fields like engineering, design, and medical studies while working on real-world projects. They engage with industry professionals, use applied technology, and develop critical thinking skills.

More examples: [Amazon future engineer](#) [BECOME](#)

Career Exploration in high school

Program High School

whole or half year option, students experience up to 8 different career programs, for 5 weeks each. It is a public program provided in 4 locations by the US Board of Cooperative Educational Services (BOCES) of ERIE 1 (19 school districts of NY State)

Explore STEM and pathways to STEM

Program Primary Middle High School

extra-curricular programs offered by a private educational travel America company that provides n20 different career, leadership, and technology programs that take place in cities across the United States and the world part of the [WorldStrides](#) company.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 2026-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan, in particular the "STEM skills foundries" centres through which students experience and explore in-demand STEM career option in relation to EU priorities with the inclusion of local actors and take informed career choices. (3.2 pg. 10, "Pilot in 2026 the development of STEM skills foundries in strategic sectors by involving companies to mentor young student entrepreneurs, in cooperation with vocational education and training providers and with higher education institutions, providing them access to their laboratories, technical infrastructures and equipment, development of intellectual property (IP), as well as facilitating access to venture capital. This should also bring together VET and higher education providers, talented VET and higher education students and the world of finance, particularly venture capital")

Related policy recommendations: SENSE

Evidence: [Visher et al., 2013](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Integrate STEAM education in Horizon Europe Pillar 2 calls, in particular Cluster 2

Integrating STEAM education into the Green Deal initiatives to provide students (especially in secondary and tertiary education) with the interdisciplinary skills needed to address complex issues like climate change. STEAM education should explicitly promote critical thinking and the ability to reflect on the ethical, political, and societal dimensions of technology and design, recognising that these are not neutral.

Examples

HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-11

Project (Funded)

Non formal

The HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-11 is a funding opportunity under the Horizon Europe program, aimed at using arts and creative sectors to engage the public in protecting and restoring aquatic environments. Projects are encouraged to collaborate with the Creative Europe program and align with the New European Bauhaus initiatives, particularly in coastal and maritime regions.

More examples: [PREPSOIL Project \(Mission Soil\)](#)

LOESS Project (Mission Soil)

Project (Funded)

Primary

Middle

High School

Non formal

hands-on soil education through community-engaged research and learning, including activities tailored for schools to foster practical understanding of soil-related issues and the “Mooc soil education: an integrated stem approach”

Neuroclima (Mission Adaptation)

Project (Funded)

Toolkit

Non formal

the project will deliver three toolkits for stakeholders and citizens for the green transition towards combating climate change: (1) participatory design, (2) creative writing and (3) cinematography, animation, and performing arts. These toolkits foster inclusive and widespread participation, educate citizens of all ages, developing essential skills among educators, policymakers, decision-makers, and others in public governance to educate citizens about climate-related initiatives, gather feedback, and promote innovative participatory policy co-design.

Potential funding instrument

Embed STEAM and industry/societal needs in Horizon Europe Pillar 2, cluster 2 destination 3 calls on education

Suggested time frame: 26-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to leverage existing funding instruments

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 5](#) [SENSE recommendation 5](#)

Evidence: [SEER D3.2](#) [Cedefop \(2023c\)](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Doctoral network on STEAM

Develop doctoral networks across universities and with industry partners to promote STEAM competence of PhD candidates and research on STEAM effectiveness, including strong monitoring skills and knowledge of randomized control trials

Examples

STEP CHANGE

Program PhD

interdisciplinary doctoral program at Politecnico di Milano is a cross-departmental doctoral program in Science, Technology, and Policy for Sustainable Change, hosted at the Electronic Engineering department, focused on sustainability and policy implications of technical research

CoDesign4Transitions

Program PhD

a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Doctoral Networks programme. The doctoral researchers carry out new research and develop skills at the intersection of co-design, sustainability, service and systems design, democratic innovation, and climate transitions

J-PAL policy action lab

Online resource University

provides training in conducting and evaluation randomized control trials

Potential funding instrument

Marie Skłodowska-Curie joint and industrial doctorates

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the plan (pg.4)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

B. Pilot STEM education centres for school education, including VET schools, across the EU with the goal of improving how STEM is delivered and experienced in primary and secondary education. Supported by Erasmus+, these centres will create dynamic learning **ecosystems** that drive innovation in STEM teaching and learning in schools, by stepping up cooperation with businesses, science museums, STEM organisations, libraries, cultural associations, creative industries, universities and research institutions.

STEAM entrepreneurship education

Research should be funded to investigate how to foster entrepreneurship in STEAM through secondary and tertiary programs, for example developing highschool programs and university degrees focused on supporting learners to develop their own businesses, as well as experimenting with microfunding and networks with SMEs and businesses

Examples

BUILD program

Program Middle High school

entrepreneurship programs from few hours to 3 years, embedded in The school program (USA)

Switzerland Venture program

Program University Non formal

the state-financed start-up programs, competition and funds are potentially recognized as college credits and promoted in universities with a focus on technological startups

High School Entrepreneurship

Program High School

program at Berkley university: 2 week program for 50 students per year supported to develop a business plan at the University campus

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 3 EIT and EIE

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the plan: "Provide dedicated training on innovation, entrepreneurship and IP management to 200 000 STEM higher education students, academics and staff by 2028, building on the EIT Higher Education Institutions Initiative in synergy with the European Universities alliances and the EIT knowledge and innovation communities." (pg. 10)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: Poggesi et al., 2020

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Effectiveness of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning paradigms to support learning preferences and needs of diverse learners to increase inclusivity and improve skills

Longitudinal study to systematically test a variety of STEAM and transdisciplinary learning options to support diverse learning preferences and diverse assessment (skills-based), integrating the EU Digital Compass and Life Comp. To support the EU and Member States in defining and adopting a unified STEAM education strategy, research should be conducted to on the effectiveness of educational paradigms and available learning options to replace or heavily revise traditional national education paradigms. Interdisciplinary skills-based (rather than knowledge-based) educations, focused on real word challenges, can provide several economic benefits to European nations, off-setting the cost of a systemic change to the EU educational system. Research should test (i.e., with experimental trials) multiple STEAM and transdisciplinary (existing or new) learning approaches and evaluate which approach is most effective for which type of learner, including learners with disabilities or belonging to vulnerable groups (incl. intersectionality); such program include Universal Design for Learning (to be applied to STEAM education), the International Bacchalaureate with STEM (in particular the Career-related Program), the Finnish STEM education program, etc.

Examples

H-Farm

Centre Program Primary-High school University

a secondary education teaching program based on the holistic International Bacchalaureate curriculum expanded to include STEM in collaboration with the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), integrates science, research, and innovation, fostering interdisciplinary learning and technological advancements in education and cultural heritage. The International Bacchalaureate has proven more successful than national curricula in improving students skills (Dulun& Lane, 2023)

School of Humanity (online middle and high school)

Centre Middle High school

developed in the US with learning hubs worldwide, it partners with schools and with industries. It received several awards and it is based on a balance of interactive online learning, with time for offline, parent-led activities. Instead of subjects, learners have daily workshops.

UDL-BOE Blended learning in schools

Project (Funded)

Interactive tool Middle High school

a project funded by Erasmus+ it focuses on developing practical tools to help teachers deliver effective and engaging learning in a digital space, addressing two key areas: inclusion and digital pedagogical competences, with the main target group being second-level teachers. The approach will be based on the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework (Cast.org), an inclusive approach to teaching and learning that offers all students an equal opportunity to fulfil their potential. This framework offers students different options for accessing, building and internalising learning.

More examples: IN-STEAM

[International Baccalaureate transdisciplinary program](#)

[IB in public schools](#)
[IB in Greece](#)

[SpicE academy](#)
[Still I rise](#)

Teacher Academy course "Universal Design for Learning: Strategies and Digital Tools to Support All Learners" and "Multi-Tiered Support System (MTSS) and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) for Academic and Behavioral Growth"

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 destination "Innovative Research on Social and Economic Transformations" and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action expands the plan to broaden its impact on under-represented and marginalized groups and increase employability.

Related policy recommendations: [SEER D7.2](#) [Road-STEAMer recommendation 7 D3.3](#)

Evidence: [Dulun& Lane, 2023](#) [Thoma, Farassopoulos & Lousta, 2023](#) [Road-STEAMer D4.2](#) [Quigley et al., 2019](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Development and testing of a EU transdisciplinary STEAM-focused curriculum in lighthouse institutions

Co-design and deployment of a variety of options for a STEAM holistic curriculum to be tested in longitudinal large scale control trials to derive evidence to inform policy decisions (Banerjee & Duflo, 2009) for step-by-step progressive pathways, taking into account the STEAM criteria (Collaboration, Disciplinary inter-relationships, Thinking-making-doing, Creativity, Real-world connection, and Inclusion / Personalisation / Empowerment) and EU priorities (focus on skills-based education, digital skills, industry relations, etc.). To inform policies on intersectionality, studies should investigate the effectiveness of STEAM programs and holistic curriculum by variables of vulnerability (gender, country, disability, special learning needs, family background, family support, etc.), and teachers/lecturer ability of diverse curricula and teaching approaches, including a holistic curriculum based on challenges (such as climate change and health instead of subjects)

Examples

Roadsteamer STEAM criteria

H-Farm Curriculum Primary School Middle High School

A secondary education teaching program based on the holistic International Bacchaurate curriculum expanded to include STEM in collaboration with the Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), integrates science, research, and innovation, fostering interdisciplinary learning and technological advancements in education and cultural heritage.

IB Silicon Valley

Curriculum Middle

The holistic International Bacchaurate curriculum Middle Years Programme (MYP) is enhanced with arts curriculum to encourages students to engage in both visual and performing arts, fostering interdisciplinary connections between artistic expression and STEM subjects. Through inquiry-based learning, students develop skills in creativity, communication, and innovation, essential for STEAM education.

Potential funding instrument

Horizon, Pillar 2 and WIDERA

More examples: [India development of national curricula](#) [International Bacchalaureate transdisciplinary program](#) [IB in Public Schools](#) [IB in Greece](#) [Still I rise](#)

Suggested time frame: After action “Transnational definition and design of what is a STEAM holistic curriculum and school”; FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

The action expands the scope providing indications for conducting extensive research on the assessment of actions to inform policy making (3.2 pg. 8, In 2025, set up a European STEM Executive Panel at top business/political/administrative level to advise on strategic issues including curriculum modernisation, industry feedback on skills needs across industrial sectors, innovative teaching and content, and embedding academic-business cooperation in STEM education. The STEM Panel would provide actionable recommendations to foster close cooperation between business and STEM education to the European Skills High Level Board and make the results of its work publicly available to any other interested party.)

Related policy recommendations: [Road-STEAMer recommendation 1, D3.3](#) [SENSE recommendation 1](#)

Evidence: [Road-STEAMer D2.3](#) [SENSE D4.4](#) [SEER D3.2](#) [JRC et al 2024](#) [Banerjee & Duflo, 2009](#) [Road-STEAMer-D4.1](#) [Road-STEAMer-D2.2](#) [Durall, Carter & Burns 2022](#)

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

EU University alliance on STEAM

Support the creation of a European Universities alliance on STEM and STEAM education.

Examples

CIVIS

Course

Online resource

University

PhD

It is Europe's Civic University Alliance, bringing together a community of more than 470,000 students and 58,000 staff members. It is the fruit of the special collaboration between 11 leading research higher education institutions across Europe.

EU STEM coalition

Online resource

Non formal

It is not focused specifically on universities but includes several typologies of European STEM and STEM actors

Potential funding instrument

European University Initiative;

Erasmus+ and National funds

Suggested time frame: 2026-27

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the alliance of universities for STEM education along with the STEAM education (3.2, pg. 9 "Working towards a European degree for engineers, by building on the European Universities alliances and ongoing Erasmus+ pilots, considering the needs of employers.")

Related policy recommendations: [Coming soon]

Evidence: SEER D3.2 SEER D2.2

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Joint diplomas, degrees, microcredentials with industry/civic organizations - fast track recognition at EU level

Map and investigate best practices of joint programs between secondary/tertiary education providers with companies and/or civic organizations, in providing technical, agile and solid education aligned with market developments, credited by educational institutions and partially funded by companies and organizations. Investigate how educational institutions can effectively become facilitators of the establishment of academic programs that are co-designed with – and co-funded by - industrial and societal players that guarantee national and EU learning standards for credited education, including EU microcredentials for life long learning.

Examples

China fast-tracking university majors in weeks

Secondary education level:

IB Career-related Programme

Program High school

Education framework for students aged 16-19, combining academic study with career-focused learning, including traditional courses, career-related studies, personal and professional skills development.

More examples:

Alfa Academy school-industry partnership

STEAMhouse

Tertiary education level:

Vocational tertiary education (Universities of Applied Sciences /Fachhochschule/ Haute Ecole Spécialisée /ITS joint programs with industries

Applied tertiary education in joint programs with industry and non-commercial partners. Examples:

ITS Academy Machina Lonati (Italy), provides tertiary vocational education in STEAM (es. fashion tech). ITS programs are recognized across Europe as vocational tertiary education. Tertiary Formal

ITS Feralpi (Italy) paid a full salary to students to learn steel industry management. Tertiary Formal

Universities: Tertiary Formal

Double degrees, such as Politecnico di Milano Double degree in Management Engineering and Product Service System Design

Potential funding instrument

Horizon Europe Cluster 2 and Erasmus+

Suggested time frame: 26-27 and FP10 (2028-34)

Alignment with STEM Education Strategic Plan 2025

This action aligns with the STEM strategy plan to design effective joint programs and microcredentials collaborating with educational institutions, businesses and industries. (3.2 pg. 10, “ i) boost the available range of joint programmes and microcredentials in STEM, including with a STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) educational approach”)

Related policy recommendations: Road-STEAMer recommendation 6

Evidence: SEER D3.1 SEER D3.2

[Provide feedback and suggestions on the portal](#)

Funding Instruments

Horizon

Erasmus+

Funds on digital; other funds and policy instruments

● *Projects*

STEAM4SEN

Description

Inclusive and innovative STE(A)M education for students with special education needs.

Time-frame: 2019 - 2022

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

Girls Self-ESTEAM

Description

Empowering girls through digital and entrepreneurial competencies to follow a career in ESTEAM

Time-frame: 2023 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

 Projects

ATS STEM

Description

Assessment of Transversal Skills in STEM was a policy experimentation project conducted across 8 EU countries aiming to enhance digital assessment of second level students' transversal skills in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics).

Time-frame: 2020 - 2022

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

 Projects

Marine Mammals

Description

Using marine mammals for making science education and science careers attractive for young people, H2020-SEAC-2015-1 CSA that took place in 2016-2019 (1.797 M€)

Time-frame: 2016 - 2019

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-SEAC-2015-1 CSA that took place in 2016-2019 (1.797 M€)

● *Projects*

STEMonEDU

Description

aimed to increase the adoption and impact of STE(A)M education by investing in the community of stakeholders and the professional development of educators. Through co-design it developed the MOOC "Professional development of STE(A)M educators".

Time-frame: 2020 - 2022

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

REGGAE

Description

Researchers for European Green Growth And Education (REGGAE), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions MSCA-NIGHT-2020bis - European Researchers' Night , CSA that took place in 2021 (0.153 M€)

Time-frame: 2021

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions MSCA-NIGHT-2020bis - European Researchers' Night , CSA that took place in 2021 (0.153 M€)

● *Projects*

STORIES

Description

Stories of Tomorrow - Students Visions on the Future of Space Exploration, H2020-ICT-2016-1 RIA that took place in 2017-2019 (2.703 M€)

Time-frame: 2017 - 2019

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-ICT-2016-1 RIA that took place in 2017-2019 (2.703 M€)

● *Projects*

Choice

Description

The project aimed to promote and improve STEM education at schools by designing innovative Open Educational Resources (OERs) collected in a MOOC, policy recommendations and teachers training resources.

Time-frame: 2020 - 2022

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

PERFORM

Description

Participatory Engagement with Scientific and Technological Research through Performance (PERFORM), H2020-SEAC-2014-1 RIA that took place in 2015-2018 (1.997 M€)

Time-frame: 2015 - 2018

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-SEAC-2014-1 RIA that took place in 2015-2018 (1.997 M€)

 Projects

Cream project

Description

The CREAM project (2021–2024) is an Erasmus+ initiative that integrates creative writing with STEAM education through Creative Writing Labs (CWLs). Aimed at secondary school students, it uses storytelling to enhance engagement, creativity, and problem-solving in science-related subjects. Piloted across several European countries, the project produced toolkits, policy briefs, and videos to support wider adoption in classrooms.

Time-frame: 2021 - 2024

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

Learn STEM

Description

Innovative Model of learning STEM in secondary schools. It aimed to product LEARN STEM Pedagogical Model, a definition of LEARN STEM Teacher Training Programme, the Design and test of the LEARN STEM online learning environment on the topics of: recycling, pollution, nature, climate.

Time-frame: 2021 - 2023

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

School As Living Labs

Description

Schools as Living Labs, H2020-SwafS-2019-2-two-stage CSA that took place in 2020-2023 (1.51 M€)

Time-frame: 2020 - 2023

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-SwafS-2019-2-two-stage CSA that took place in 2020-2023 (1.51 M€)

● *Projects*

OTTER

Description

Outdoor Science Education for a Sustainable Future, H2020-SwafS-2020-2-two-stage CSA took place in 2021-2024 (1 59M€)

Time-frame: 2021 - 2024

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-SwafS-2020-2-two-stage CSA took place in 2021-2024 (1 59M€)

● *Projects*

STE(A)M Learning Ecologies

Description

To be done

Time-frame: 2023 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: European Research Area (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01)

● *Projects*

STEAMbrace

Description

This project aims to bridge the current gender gap in STEM fields by unlocking the potential of STEAM (STEM + Arts) education approach for future European innovators, especially women. Thus, this project will establish a coordination Alliance at European level and develop numerous networking and educational activities using creative thinking and a scientific evidence-based approach. financed with 2.88 M€

Time-frame: 2024 - 2026

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: [Research and innovation on cultural heritage and CCIs - 2023 \(HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01\)](#)

● *Projects*

VERTIGO

Description

Adding socio-economic value to industry through the integration of artists in research and open innovation processes, H2020-ICT-2016-1 CSA that took place in 2016-2020 (4.258 M€)

Time-frame: 2016 - 2020

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-ICT-2016-1 CSA that took place in 2016-2020 (4.258 M€)

● *Projects*

BLOOM

Description

Boosting European citizens knowledge and awareness of bioeconomy, H2020-BB-2017-1 CSA that took place in 2017-2020 (2.4 M€) - although not specific on STEM

Time-frame: 2017 - 2020

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-BB-2017-1 CSA that took place in 2017-2020 (2.4 M€)

● *Projects*

STEAM INC

Description

STEAM INC was an Erasmus+ project (2019–2022) that united seven European institutions to explore how integrating Arts into STEM (STEAM) can enhance higher education. It developed a shared STEAM definition, tested teaching methods, and created tools to support interdisciplinary, creative, and innovative learning.

Time-frame: 2019 - 2023

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

EuroSTEAM

Description

The project aimed to provide accessible STEAM camps throughout Europe which teachers used in their classrooms to enhance the students experience of the STEAM subjects.

Time-frame: 2016 - 2019

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

CREATIONS

Description

H2020-SEAC-2014-1 CSA that took place in 2015-2018 (1.979 M€)

Time-frame: 2015 - 2018

Funding Instrument: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-SEAC-2014-1 CSA that took place in 2015-2018 (1.979 M€)

● *Projects*

STE(A)M IT

Description

Innovative and cross-disciplinary approaches to STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) teaching.

Time-frame: 2019 - 2022

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

The Levers for Climate (LEVERS)

Description

To be done

Time-frame: 2023 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: European Research Area (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01)

 Projects

ICSE Science Factory

Description

International Centre for STEM education Science Factory

Time-frame: 2023 - 2026

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: [European Research Area \(HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01\)](#)

● *Projects*

EU STEM Coalition

Description

EU's main network of regional/national STEM platforms. IT fosters EU-wide cooperation between national STEM platforms.

Time-frame: 2012 - Present

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

 Projects

ESTEAM Fest

Description

Organized by European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), ESTEAM stands for Entrepreneurship, Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics. Over the three years of the project STEAM events are organised in 19 EU Member States with the aim to boost women and girls' competences, inspire them, and give them the chance to connect with like-minded peers.

Time-frame: 2022 - 2024

Funding Instrument: European Innovation Council, SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)

● *Projects*

STREAM IT

Description

"St(R)E(A)M It/Streaming Girls And Women Into Steam Education, Innovation And Research" (2024-26 financed with 1.85 M€). It aims to bridge persistent gender gaps in STEM education, research and innovation by implementing the European Manifesto for gender-inclusive STE(A)M education and careers. financed with 2.88 M€

Time-frame: 2024 - 2026

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

Call: [Enhancing the European R&I system \(HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01\)](#)

● *Projects*

EU STEM Coalition

Description

EU's main network of regional/national STEM platforms. IT fosters EU-wide cooperation between national STEM platforms.

Time-frame: 2012 - Present

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

SpicE project

Description

Comprises a bundle of actions aims to enhance Primary Education Teachers' ability to implement effective STEAM instruction for protecting students with Mild Disabilities (Special Education) from educational and social exclusion. STEAM is used both as the means and as the purpose for enabling a much-needed shift in Special Education in Primary Education both at an in-service and pre-service level.

Time-frame: 2022 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Erasmus +

● *Projects*

SENSE

Description

SENSE aims to produce a New European Roadmap to STEAM Education that puts forward an art-integrative science education, grounded into a sensory and participatory approach to STEAM education.

SENSE is centering its roadmap around STEAM pedagogical model and exemplary hands-on STEAM activities that have been implemented across its SENSE.STEAM labs, and have enabled the creation of a learning companion for developing STEAM learning sequences by educational practitioners. This has been further supplemented with toolkits for the assessment of spatial requirements as well as inclusive social creativity.

Source: <https://sense-steam.eu/>

Time-frame: 2022 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

● *Projects*

SEER

Description

The overarching objective of the SEER project is to provide a set of roadmaps that will pave the way for the policy and institutional changes necessary for the large-scale implementation and mainstreaming of STE(A)M education in Europe. The SEER will synthesise the status of STE(A)M Education and evaluate national and international policies to understand which policy settings best support STE(A)M education. This analysis and resulting recommendations will be provided to Ministries of Education and EU policy makers to support policy improvements in Europe. In addition, STE(A)M initiatives and EU funded projects of all teaching levels will be mapped and evaluated, identifying educational strategies that provide the best outcomes for teachers and students.

Source: <https://www.scientix.eu/community/partner-projects/the-seer#about>

Time-frame: 2022 - 2025

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe

What is STEAM

STEM education is a teaching practice challenging the view that science, technology, engineering and mathematics are detached disciplines that require unique and context-sensitive methodologies and content.

Instead, it asserts that they need to be treated holistically, as a unique field of both research and application in the classroom. STEM's latest version attempts to incorporate the arts (STEAM), with an aim to transform its teaching to a more attractive and impactful exercise. Modern STEAM approaches also integrate problem-solving and inquiry-based learning, developing both hard and soft capabilities, as properly developed in the framework of 21st Century skills.

EQUITY as an underlying value of all STEAM practices

<https://www.road-steamer.eu/>

Contact: sabrina.bresciani@polimi.it

Conceptual framework for STEAM Education

Road-STEAMer conducted a comprehensive analysis of the ways STEAM education has been theorized and conceptualized in secondary-tertiary and open-science/open-schooling practices

We identified a relational ontology underpinning STEAM Education

STEAM Education is understood as always involving the relationships between different elements of STEAM education practice, including disciplines, people, materials, and the environment

Our analysis identified four groups of approaches

26 theories and conceptual frameworks drawn from the literature were analysed thematically

*Conducted by the University of Exeter
The theories of the four approaches are listed alphabetically and do not represent a hierarchy

Read our full report